

An Up-To-Date Checklist of Turkish Lygaeoidea (excluding Rhyparochromidae) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) with additional records

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ABSTRACT: In this study, an updated list of the Turkish Lygaeoidea superfamily (excluding Rhyparochromidae) is presented along with the results obtained from field studies carried out in 91 localities with different habitat characteristics in 5 Provinces in the Thrace Region between 2015 and 2020. As a result of the evaluation of materials collected in the region, 53 species belonging to 7 families were identified of which 16 are first records for Turkish Thrace. The first exact locality records were given for two species from the Thrace Region. In addition, as a result of reviewing the studies carried out in Türkiye so far, it has been determined that 49 genera and 146 species/subspecies belonging to 10 families (Artheneidae, Berytidae, Blissidae, Cymidae, Geocoridae, Heterogastridae, Lygaeidae, Oxycarenidae, Pachygronthidae, Piesmatidae) from the Lygaeoidea superfamily are distributed, but 7 of these species need to be confirmed. The distributions of the species are handled separately for the European part (Thrace) of Türkiye and the Asian part (Anatolia). With the 16 new records obtained in this study, 71 species are from European Türkiye and 137 species are from Asian Türkiye (2 species are distributed only in European Türkiye, 68 species only in Asian Türkiye and 69 species in both parts). The type localities of 7 species are in Türkiye (Anatolia) and 2 species of them are endemic to Anatolia.

KEYWORDS: Heteroptera, Lygaeoidea, Türkiye, Anatolia, Turkish Thrace, check-list, faunistic

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INTRODUCTION

Türkiye consists of two peninsulas (Thrace and Anatolia) located on two continents (Europe and Asia), and its actual area, including lakes and islands, is 814,578 km² and its projection area is 783,562 km².

It is a large country with a roughly rectangular shape, located between the 36° and 42° north parallels and the 26° and 45° east meridians. The part called Anatolia, also known as the Asian Türkiye, has an area of 755,688 km² and covers the largest part of the country.

Turkish Thrace (European Türkiye), located at the southeastern part of the European continent, has an area of 23,764 km², corresponding to 3% of the country.

These two peninsulas are separated by the Dardanelles and Bosphorus straits and the Marmara Sea. The country has borders with Bulgaria and Greece in the northwest, Georgia in the northeast, Armenia, Iran and Azerbaijan (Nakhichevan) in the east, and Iraq and Syria in the southeast.

It is surrounded by Cyprus Island and the Mediterranean Sea in the south, the Aegean Sea in the west, and the Black Sea in the north. Türkiye is geographically divided into 7 regions (Marmara, including the Thrace, Aegean, Mediterranean, Central Anatolia, Black Sea, Eastern Anatolia and Southeastern Anatolia) and administratively 81 Provinces (76 of which are only in Anatolia, 3 only in Thrace and Çanakkale and İstanbul in both regions (Figure 1.) (Anonym 2024).

Figure 1. Map of Türkiye with a position of the major (bio)geographic regions and of the Provinces (Hürriyet com.tr)

More than half of Türkiye consists of high areas with an altitude exceeding 1,000 meters.

The average altitude is 1141 meters. Approximately one-third of the country is covered by medium–altitude plains, plateaus and mountains, and 10% is covered by low areas. The highest and mountainous areas are located in the eastern part. The northern part is divided into the Northern Anatolian Mountains, while The Taurus Mountains cover the

southern, eastern and southeastern parts.

There are agriculturally productive delta plains on the Black Sea, Mediterranean and Aegean Sea coasts, and lake bottom plains in Central Anatolia. The most common type of plains are tectonic plains located on fault lines. Plateaus are mostly found in the Eastern Black Sea Region and Central Anatolia (Figure 2.) (Anonym 2024)

Figure 2. Topographic map of Türkiye (Wikipedia)

The geographical position of Türkiye at the junction of the African–Asian and the European continents, makes the country serve as a natural bridge where many species migrate between these continents. This structure, combined with the variable land structure, creates a rich diversity of plant species and plant communities. About 11000 plant taxa are known to naturally spread in Türkiye, among which 35% (≈ 3500) are endemic. 5 main vegetation types are dominant in Türkiye. These are Forest, Maki, Garig, Steppe and Alpine vegetation types. Forest vegetation, one of the most important vegetation types with different structures and characteristics, constitutes approximately 27% of the country's area. Forest vegetation shows significant diversity according to the European Siberian, Mediterranean and Iran–Turanian flora areas (Aksoy et al., 2014).

Türkiye has gained the characteristics of a small continent in terms of biodiversity due to being involved in three biogeographic regions (Europe–Siberia, Mediterranean and Iran–Turan) and their transition zones, being a bridge between two continents, and its variable topography and climate that provide many different macro- or micro- habitats. Türkiye has forest, mountain, steppe, wetland, coastal and

marine ecosystems and different forms and combinations of these ecosystems. In addition, the constantly changing tectonic evolution of Anatolia in Tertiary and Quaternary periods (Anatolia or its main continent, the Aegean plate, connected with the European, Arabian, Iranian and Caucasian plates many times throughout the Tertiary, especially in the Miocene) enabled faunal changes and its topographic structure, and the region became an important shelter during the Quaternary Ice Age due to its different ecological and climatic conditions.. All these features supported the biodiversity and endemic species formation in Türkiye (Demirsoy, 1996; Çıplak, 2003). As with many vertebrate and invertebrate groups, findings regarding Heteroptera reveal the species richness in Türkiye. Fent et al. (2011) listed 100 species/subspecies from aquatic and semi-aquatic Heteroptera. Fent & Dursun (2022) presented 174 species/subspecies in their checklist of the family Pentatomidae. Çerçi et al. (2024) stated that the number of Heteroptera species in Türkiye is around 1668, considering the results of available faunistic studies conducted in the country so far, together with 6 new species they recently described.

Turkish Thrace is the smallest part of

Turkish territory located in the South-eastern corner of the Balkan Peninsula. The region generally consists of low altitudes, with an average altitude of 180 m above sea level, well below the Türkiye average of 1141 m. Altitudes between 0–250 m constitute 83.1% of Turkish Thrace, altitudes between 250–500 m constitute 13.4%, and altitudes between 500–1000 m constitute 3.5%. The highest point of the region is Mahya Hill (1035 m.) located in the Istranca Mountain range. Istranca Mountains in the north, Belgrad Forests in the northeast, and Ganos Mountains in the south of the region are covered with moist type forests in high places. Southern slopes of the Istranca Mountains (up to 500–600 m), Çatalca Peninsula, Koru Mountains and Gelibolu Peninsula in the south have dry oak forests. In the coastal area, there is a Mediterranean plant community dominated by maquis. In the central part of the Thrace Region, the Ergene Basin lies, which consists of large agricultural lands and has the characteristics of an anthropogenic steppe (Dönmez, 1969).

The Lygaeoidea is a very large süper-family of the suborder Heteroptera, consisting of true bugs that include seed bugs and their allies, with more than 4,600 described species belonging to 16 families worldwide. Most species in this group feed on seeds or sap, but a few are predatory. The Lygaeoidea superfamily has 257 genera, 1164 species and 52 subspecies belonging to 15 families in the Palaearctic Region (Aukema, 2018). The number of species of families in the Palaearctic Region is as follows: Artheneidae 4 genera, 16 species; Berytidae 15 genera, 60 species, 6 subspecies; Blissidae 9 genera, 60 species; Colobathristidae 2 genera, 7 species; Cymidae, 2 genera, 18 species; Geocoridae 6 genera, 77 species, 9 subspecies; Heterogastridae 10 genera, 34 species; Lygaeidae 32 genera, 160 species, 16 subspecies; Malcidae 3 genera, 32 species, 1 subspecies; Meschiidae 1 genus 1 species; Ninidae 3 genera, 7 species; Oxycarenidae 19 genera, 58 species, 6 subspecies; Pachygronthidae 6

genera, 17 species, 3 subspecies, Piesmatidae 2 genera 21 species and Rhyparochromidae 143 genera, 596 species and 11 subspecies (Aukema, 2018).

The highest number of species belongs to the Rhyparochromidae family, followed by the Lygaeidae family.

The Artheneidae, Blissidae, Cymidae, Geocoridae, Heterogastridae, Oxycarenidae, Pachygronthidae and Rhyparochromidae families, which were previously subfamilies of the Lygaeidae family but were raised to the family level by Henry (1997), are spread on all continents and are the second largest after Miridae in the world with 4000 species belonging to 650 genera.

The studies on the Lygaeoidea süper-family in Türkiye were carried out by foreign researchers in the last quarter of the 19th century. Except for the recent studies, in these studies, the family Lygaeidae is given in its former form (subfamilies were not elevated to family status). Horváth (1883, 1894, 1898, 1901, 1905, 1916, 1918, 1919) recorded many species (with a new species) from many localities of Anatolia, especially in western (Bursa, Aydın, İstanbul), southern and eastern Anatolia. Reuter, (1890, 1895), Puton & Noulhier (1895), Gadeau de Kerville (1939) and Esherich (1987) gave species records from various Provinces of Anatolia, especially Ankara and İzmir. Fahringer (1922) presented species records from the Belgrad Forests in the European part of İstanbul and the south of Anatolia, and Kritshenko (1918, 1924) presented species records from various localities in Eastern Anatolia, especially Kars. Linnavuori, (1953, 1965) recorded 24 species from various localities, mostly in Western Anatolia. When Hoberlandt (1956) evaluated his records from Provinces such as Edirne in the Thrace Region, Bolu Ankara, Adana, Afyon, Mersin, and Gaziantep in Anatolia, as well as other records given from Türkiye up to that time, he reported 171 species, one of which was new, belonging to the Lygaeoidea superfamily. In the following years, Seidenstücker, (1953a, b, 1957, 1958,

1960a, b, 1965) recorded a new species and a new subspecies from the family Berytidae with others records. Wagner (1959, 1966), Péricart (1999a, b), Matocq et al. (2000, 2010, 2014), and Şerban (2010) gave some faunistic records belonging to the Lygaeoidea superfamily in different Provinces in Anatolia and Thrace.

The studies of local researchers started later and have continued until today. Aysev (1974) identified 32 species in her study on the Lygaeidae family in the Aegean Region. Çağatay, (1986, 1988, 1989a, b, 1995) has provided many records as well as male genital studies of various subfamilies.

Lodos et al. (1978) in their study to determine the pest fauna of the Marmara and Aegean Regions, identified 64 species belonging to 9 subfamilies from the Lygaeidae family. Lodos et al. (1999), in their detailed study to identify the pest fauna in the Western Black Sea, Central Anatolia and Mediterranean Regions, recorded 149 species belonging to 12 subfamilies of the Lygaeidae family in these three regions. Çakır & Önder (1990) conducted a detailed study on the Geocorinae subfamily in Türkiye and identified 8 species from this subfamily, which includes important predator species. Apart from these studies, many researchers have conducted studies on Lygaeoidea in various regions in Thrace and Anatolia (Önder et al., 1981, 1983, 1984; Kiyak, 1990, 1993, 2000, 2016a b; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Fent & Aktaç, 2008; Kiyak & Akar, 2010; Öncül-Abacıgil et al., 2010; Fent, 2011; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2022; Fent & Dursun, 2016a b; Çerçi et al., 2018, 2022; Yazıcı, 2019, 2022a, b; Özgen et al., 2021a-c; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Fent & Okyar, 2022; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023a b; Yence & Fent, 2023).

The studies on the Thrace Region so far are limited. The first records belong to foreign researchers and started in the early 1900s.

Horváth (1918) recorded 8 species from

İstanbul, Fahringer (1922) recorded 5 species from İstanbul, Hoberlandt (1956) recorded 32 species from Edirne, and Wagner (1966) recorded 2 species.

While listing the Heteroptera of the Balkan Peninsula, Josifov (1986) recorded 43 species from Turkish Thrace without specifying locality (as ET).

Lodos et al. (1978), in their study to determine the pest fauna of the Marmara and Aegean Regions, identified 22 species in the Thrace part. Önder et al. (1984), in their study in Edirne using light traps, identified 17 species, and Fent & Aktaç, (2008), in their study on the determination of adult wintering Heteroptera species in Edirne, identified 16 species from Lygaeidae.

While Önder et al. (2006) gave 41 species/subspecies in the Turkish catalogue, Péricart (2001a, b) reported 66 species/subspecies from Lygaeidae and Berytidae from the Thrace Region (35 of Thrace Region (35 of these species are from the Rhyparochoriminae subfamily) in the Palaearctic catalogue.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The field studies were carried out in 91 different localities in the Thrace Region during the spring-autumn periods between 2015–2020 (Table 1., Figure 3.).

The research material was captured with the help of the insect nets from herbaceous plants, a Japanese umbrella from trees and bushes, and a suction tube from the soil and plant roots.

In addition to this material, samples collected from various Provinces in Anatolia by A. Dursun (second author) were given under Asian Türkiye.

To identify the specimens, we used the following keys: Stichel (1956-1962) and Péricart (1999a, b). In addition, the studies carried out in Türkiye to date have been scanned and the species and the Provinces where they are distributed are given. Palaearctic distributions of the species are taken from Aukema (2018).

Table 1. Studied localities in Thrace Region, altitudes, coordinates and sampling dates

L o c · n o	Locality	A l t i t u d e	Coordinate	Sampling date
1	Edirne (Uzunköprü–Saçlımüsellim)	69 m	41°25'746N 26°37'57E	13.06.2015
2	Kırklareli (Kofçaz–Kadıköy)	387 m	41°48'40N 27°10'44E	17.06.2015
3	Tekirdağ (Hayrabolu–Danişment)	77 m	41°17'59N 26°57'78E	18.06.2015
4	Tekirdağ (Hayrabolu–between Danişment–Çerkezmüsellim)	96 m	41°16'19N 27°1'34E	18.06.2015
5	Kırklareli (Pehlivanköy)	41 m	41° 20'45N 26°55'29E	19.06.2015
6	Kırklareli (Pınarhisar–İslambeyli)	165 m	41°42'4N 27°37'35E	21.06.2015
7	Kırklareli (between Yenice–Demirköy around sand pit)	689 m	41°44'55N 27°40'13E	21.06.2015
8	Kırklareli (Demirköy–Sislioba)	138 m	41°57'38N 27°54'48E	24.06.2015
9	Kırklareli (Demirköy–İğneada)	0 m	41°52'28N 27°59'2E	24.06.2015
10	Kırklareli (Demirköy–Boztaş)	368 m	41°54'48N 27°38'52E	25.06.2015
11	Kırklareli (Demirköy–Istranca)	403 m	41°55'46N27°36'27E	25.06.2015
12	Kırklareli (Demirköy–Hamdibey)	459 m	41°51'46N 27°45'50E	26.06.2015
13	Kırklareli (Demirköy–between Hamdibey–Yeşilce)	390 m	41°52'38N 27°42'18E	26.06.2015
14	Kırklareli (Demirköy–Longoz Forest)	19 m	41°49'16N 27°57'12E	27.06.2015
15	Kırklareli (Vize–Kıyıköy)	5 m	41°38'5N 28°5'19E	28.06.2015
16	Kırklareli (Demirköy–Sivriler)	334 m	41°46'51N 27°51'55E	28.06.2015
17	Kırklareli (Pınarhisar–Mahya Hill)	647 m	41°47'18N 27°37'56E	30.06.2015
18	Edirne (Center)	41 m	41°38'59N 26°37'24E	01.07.2015 10.10.2018
19	Edirne (Center–Uzgaç)	252 m	41°48'27N 26°24'14E	01.07.2015 08.07.2015
20	Edirne (Center–Kırköy)	252m	41°6'21N 26°43'20E	04.07.2015
21	Edirne (Center–Suakacağı)	35 m	41°50'27N 26°35'11E	05.07.2015
22	Edirne (Süleoğlu–Büyük Gerdelli village)	252 m	41°44'10N 26°56'54E	05.07.2015
23	Edirne (Lalapaşa–Ömeroba)	352m	41°55'40N 26°56'54E	15.07.2015
24	Edirne (Uzunköprü)	33 m	41°16'72N 26°40'52E	15.07.2015
25	Kırklareli (Center–Çağlayık)	453 m	42°2'5N 27°20'25E	15.08.2015
26	Tekirdağ (between Saray–Bahçeköy)	281m	41°30'43N 28°0'32E	18.08.2015
27	Tekirdağ (between Saray–Safaalan)	213 m	41°26'25N27°59'58E	18.08.2015 11.06.2016
28	İstanbul (Çatalca–Binkılıç)	215 m	41°23'55N 28°11'40E	18.08.2015
29	İstanbul (Çatalca–İhsaniye)	133 m	41°15'15N 28°23'41E	18.08.2015
30	İstanbul (Silivri–Fener Köyü)	58 m	41°8'40N 28°15'56E	19.08.2015
31	Tekirdağ (Center–Naip Köy)	105 m	40°52'59N 27°25'26E	19.08.2015
32	Tekirdağ (Center–Mermer)	112 m	40°51'22N 27°22'23E	20.08.2015
33	Tekirdağ (Şarköy–Uçmakedere)	140 m	40°47'57N 27°21'49E	20.08.2015
34	Tekirdağ (Şarköy)	120 m	40°38'15N 27°5'55E	21.08.2015
35	Tekirdağ (Şarköy–Yeniköy)	167 m	40°39'27N 27°3'34E	11.06.2017
36	Kırklareli (Center–Üsküp)	268 m	41°43'23N 27°22'45E	22.08.2015 21.05.2016 06.06.2016
37	Kırklareli (Center–Çukurpınar)	509 m	41°49'5N 27°28'10E	22.08.2015 21.05.2016
38	Edirne (Uzunköprü road)	79 m	41°19'27N 26°43'59E	27.08.2015
39	Edirne (Enez–Dalayan, Hisarlı, Karagöl, Taşaltı)	5 m	40°43'29N 26°4'57E	31.08.2015 01.09.2015 03.09.2015

40	Kırklareli (Lüleburgaz-Evrensekiz)	73 m	41°22'11N 27°29'42E	14.05.2016
41	Edirne (Süloğlu-Dam)	252 m	41°46'8N 26°54'36E	15.05.2016
42	Edirne (Uzunköprü-Çöpköy)	56 m	41°13'11N 26°49'22E	16.05.2016 08.06.2016
43	Edirne (Uzunköprü-Ömerbey)	50 m	41°15'407N 26°50'13E	16.05.2016
44	Çanakkale (Gelibolu-İlgardere)	141 m	40°18'7N 26°28'38E	17.05.2016
45	Çanakkale (between Eceabat-Kilitbahir)	7 m	40°9'31N 26°22'16E	17.05.2016
46	Çanakkale (Eceabat-between Behramlı-Şehitlik)	78 m	40° 6'27N 26°14'22E	17.05.2016
47	Edirne (Keşan- Küçük Yerlisu-Koru Mountains)	252 m	40°43'30N 26°43'52E	18.05.2016
48	Edirne (Meriç-Olacak village)	47 m	41°12'55N 26°28'25E	19.05.2016
49	Edirne (Meriç-Akıncılar road)	9 m	41°11'32N 26°31'8E	20.05.2016
50	Edirne (Meriç-Kadıondurma)	46 m	41°10'25N 26°21'18E	20.05.2016
51	Edirne (Havsa-Hasköy-Saksağan Stream)	252 m	41°39' 38N 26°53' 21E	21.05.2016
52	Kırklareli (Center-Beypınar)	544 m	41°47'58N 27°30'20E	22.05.2016 06.06.2016
53	Kırklareli (Center-Kavakdere)	152 m	41°35'54N 27°16'7E	03.06.2016
54	Kırklareli (Center-Deveçatağı)	139 m	41°34'45N 27°18'37E	04.06.2016
55	Edirne (Lalapaşa-Hacdanışment)	508 m	41°54'35N 26°49'26E	07.06.2016
56	Edirne (İpsala road)	38 m	40°57'43N 26°25'24E	08.06.2016
57	Kırklareli (Babaeski)	78 m	41°25'28N 27° 7'21E	09.06.2016
58	Kırklareli (Center-Kavaklı)	147 m	41°38'46N 27° 9'58E	09.06.2016
59	İstanbul (Çatalca-Danamandıra)	168 m	41°19'27N 28°15'44E	11.06.2016
60	İstanbul (between Çatalca-İhsaniye)	250 m	41°18'10N 28°19'56E	11.06.2016
61	İstanbul (Çatalca-Yazlık)	5 m	41°18'53N 28°31'45E	12.06.2016
62	İstanbul (Arnavutköy road)	116 m	41°16'14N 28°38'26	12.06.2016
63	İstanbul (Çatalca-Dağyenice)	95 m	41°16'34N28°29'3E	12.06.2016
64	İstanbul (Çatalca-Hisarbeyli)	75 m	41°21'56N28°28'46E	13.06.2016
65	İstanbul (Silivri-between Danamandıra-Küçüksinekli)	186 m	41°18'2N 28°14'12E	13.06.2016
66	İstanbul (Çatalca-Akalan Bridge)	158 m	41°15'15N 28°23'41E	14.06.2016
67	İstanbul (Silivri-Küçüksinekli)	156 m	41°12'55N 28°12'43E	15.06.2016
68	Kırklareli (Pınarhisar)	283 m	41°37'13N 27°30'17	16.06.2016
69	Kırklareli (Center-Üsküpdere)	219 m	41°41'13N 27°22'21E	16.06.2016
70	Edirne (Uzunköprü-Kavacık)	34 m	41°11'14N 26°39'56E	14.07.2016
71	Edirne (Uzunköprü-Çavuşlu)	100 m	41° 4' 56N 26° 47' 15E	14.07.2016
72	Edirne (Uzunköprü-Mestanlar)	151 m	41°7'11N 26°50'45E	15.07.2016
73	Kırklareli (Lüleburgaz-Kıkköy)	273 m	41°28'05N27°15'41E	15.07.2016
74	Kırklareli (Vize-Doğanca)	238 m	41°34'44N 27°36'57E	16.07.2016
75	Tekirdağ (Ergene-Esenler)	104 m	41°13'1N 27°38'54E	17.07.2016
76	Tekirdağ (Muratlı-Hanoğlu)	93 m	41°11'33N 27°21'45E	17.07.2016
77	Tekirdağ (Çorlu-next to the Unilever)	94 m	41°14'33N 27°41'59E	18.07.2016
78	Tekirdağ (Muratlı-Ballıhoca)	77 m	41°12'55N 27°30'52E	18.07.2016
79	Tekirdağ (Saray-Çaylaköy)	123 m	41°23'47N 27°52'45E	18.07.2016
80	Edirne (Keşan-Koru Mountains)	70 m	40°38'0N 26°56'28E	21.07.2016
81	Edirne (Keşan-Kocahıdır)	40 m	40°48'25N 26°25'42E	22.07.2016
82	Edirne (Keşan-Mecidiye)	53 m	40°39'26N 26°33'05E	22.07.2016
83	Edirne (Enez-Gülçavuş- coastal path)	38 m	40°37'15N 26°10'9E	23.07.2016
84	Edirne (Keşan-Karahisar)	22 m	40°45'54N 26°30'22E	24.07.2016
85	Edirne (Center-Balkan Campus)	41 m	41°38'59N 26°37'24E	08.05.2017
				16.05.2017
				28.06.2017
				21.06.2018
				29.06.2018
				01.07.2018
				25.07.2018
				03.08.2018

86	Tekirdağ (Şarköy-Uluman)	227 m	40°42'26N 27°5'55E	11.06.2017
87	Tekirdağ (Malkara-Ahmetpaşa village)	158 m	40°53'50N 26°48'57E	22.06.2017
88	Tekirdağ (Malkara-betweenYaylaköy-Yaylagöne)	189 m	40°54'34N 26°48'12E	22.06.2017
89	Tekirdağ (Malkara-Izgar village)	179 m	40°51'42N 26°48'24E	22.06.2017
90	Tekirdağ (Malkara-betweenYaylaköy-Yaylagöne)	189 m	40°54'34N 26°48'12E	22.06.2017

Figure 3. Studied localities in Thrace Region (Google Earth)

Ordo HEMIPTERA

Subordo HETEROPTERA

Infraordo PENTATOMOMORPHA

Superfamily LYGAEOIDEA Schilling, 1829

Family ARTHENEIDAE Stål, 1872

Subfamily ARTHENEINAE Stål, 1872

Tribe ARTHENEINI Stål, 1872

Genus *Artheneis* Spinola, 1837

***Arthenis alutacea* Fieber, 1861**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Aksaray, Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Denizli, Elazığ, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Iğdır, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kırıkkale, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye (Reuter, 1890; Horváth, 1894; Kiritschenko, 1918; Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Çağatay, 1988;

Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Özgen et al., 2021a; Çerçi et. al., 2022).

European Türkiye: Çanakkale, Edirne (Lodos et al., 1978; Çağatay, 1988).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Crete, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Anatolia, Middle East.

Note: Péricart (1999a) stated that all of the rich material collected by Seidenstücker, from Anatolia may belong to *Artheneis wagneri* and that the material should be checked to give the exact distribution of *A. alutacea* from Anatolia. Aukema (2018) gave the distribution of *A. alutacea* for Türkiye as "Asian Türkiye?". However, apart from Seidenstücker, other researchers also provide various records from Anatolia, which confirm its existence in Anatolia.

***Artheneis balcanica* (Kormilev, 1938)**

Asian Türkiye: Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Balıkesir, Bolu, Bursa, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Gaziantep, İzmir, Karabük, Karaman, Kastamonu, Konya, Nevşehir, Niğde, Zonguldak (Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Çağatay, 1988; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 1981, 2006; Matocq et al., 2014).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Balkans, Russia (ST), Ukraine, Asian Türkiye, Middle East and Central Asia.

Note: Widely spread throughout the peninsular part of Anatolia, except perhaps the humid strip of the northern coast; towards the East to the Euphrates (Aukema 2018).

***Artheneis foveolata* Spinola, 1837**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Erzincan, İzmir, Karabük, Karaman, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Zonguldak (Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Özbek et al., 1996; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Bosnia Hercegovina, Crete, Croatia, France, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Malta, Spain. North Africa: Algeria, Egypt?, Morocco, Tunisia. Asia: Asian Türkiye, Cyprus?

Note: Péricart (1999a) reported that this species, distributed in the Mediterranean basin, is common in the western basin, but records from the eastern basin, Egypt, and Türkiye, may belong to other related species and need to be confirmed. However, numerous findings of other researchers confirm the existence of this species in Anatolia.

***Artheneis hyrcanica* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Ankara, Aydın, Denizli, Elazığ, Hatay, Isparta, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Mersin, Tunceli (Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Kerzhner, 1997; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Matocq et al., 2014).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Greece. Asia: Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Iran, Iraq, Georgia?, Syria.

***Artheneis intricata* O5. G. Putshkov, 1969**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Niğde (Péricart, 1999a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: European Kazakhstan, Russia, Ukraine, Asian Türkiye, Central Asia, and China.

Genus *Holcocranum* Fieber, 1860

***Holcocranum saturejae* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Çanakkale Province: Between Behramlı-Şehitlik, 17.05.2016, 1 ♂; Edirne Province: Keşan-Koru Mountains, 21.07.2016, 1 ♂; Mecidiye, 22.07.2016, 1 ♂; Kocahıdır, 22.07.2016, 5 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂; Karahisar,

24.07.2016, 3 ♀♀; Uzunköprü–Çavuşlu, 14.07.2016, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; İstanbul Province: Çatalca–Danamandıra, 11.06.2016, 15 ♀♀, 10 ♂♂; Silivri–between Danamandıra–Küçüksinekli 13.06.2016, 1 ♂; Kırklareli Province: Center–Üsküp, 21.05.2016, 1 ♂; Kavakdere, 03.06.2016, 1 ♂; Deveçatağı, 04.06.2016, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Tekirdağ Province: Ergene–Esenler, 16.07.2016, 1 ♀; next to the Unilever, 17.07.2016, 1 ♂; Muratlı–Hanoğlu, 17.07.2016, 44 ♀♀, 41 ♂♂.

European Türkiye: Edirne (Önder et al., 1984, 2006; Fent & Aktaç, 2008).

Asian Türkiye: Bursa, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kocaeli, Mersin, Sakarya (Seidenstücker, 1958; Çağatay, 1988; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 1981, 2006; Çerçi et al., 2018; Fent et al., 2022; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, European and Asian Türkiye, North Africa, Transcaucasia, Middle East. Extralimital: Tropical Africa, North America (USA, introduced).

Family BERYTIDAE Fieber, 1851

Subfamily BERYTINAE Fieber, 1851

Tribe BERYTINI Fieber, 1851

Genus: *Apolymus* Fieber, 1859

Apolymus pectoralis Fieber, 1859

European Türkiye: İstanbul (Péricart, 1984)

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Ankara, Balıkesir, Bursa, Çankırı, İstanbul, İzmir, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Malatya, Mardin, Sinop, Zonguldak (Reuter, 1890; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Péricart, 1984; Morkel 2007; Dursun, 2016; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern (Balkans) and southern Europe, European and Asian Türkiye, Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia, Cyprus, Middle East.

Genus *Neides* Latreille, 1802

Neides aduncus Fieber, 1859

Asian Türkiye: Antalya, Çanakkale, Isparta, İzmir, Kocaeli, Manisa, Samsun (Linnavuori, 1953; Önder et al., 1983; Péricart, 1984; Morkel 2007).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern (Balkans) and southern Europe, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Israel.

Neides afghanus Seidenstücker, 1968

Asian Türkiye: Anatolia (without locality information) (Péricart, 2001b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Asia: Afghanistan, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Iran, Kirgizia, Tadzhikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Yemen.

Neides brevipennis Puton, 1895

Asian Türkiye: Adıyaman, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Gaziantep, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kayseri, Konya, Malatya, Mardin, Mersin, Niğde, Şanlıurfa, Van (Puton 1895; Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Seidenstücker, 1958; Péricart, 1984; Matocq et al., 2014; Kiyak, 2016a; Kemal & Koçak, 2018; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Croatia?, Asia: Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Syria, Turkmenistan, Yemen.

Note: The type locality of this species is “Asia Minor” (Péricart, 2001b).

Neides tipularius (Linnaeus, 1758)

European Türkiye: Edirne (Hoberlandt, 1956; Josifov, 1986; Önder et al., 2006)

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Ankara, Bingöl, Çankırı, Elazığ, Kars, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Niğde (Horváth, 1905; Kiritshenko, 1918, 1924; Hoberlandt, 1956; Seidenstücker, 1958; Péricart, 1984; Çağlar, 1992; Kıyak, 1993; Önder et al., 2006; Morkel 2007; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Kıyak, 2016a; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Uzbekistan.

Tribe BERYTININI Southwood & Leston, 1959

Genus *Berytinus* Kirkaldy, 1900

Subgenus *Berytinus* Kirkaldy, 1900

***Berytinus clavipes* (Fabricius, 1775)**

European Türkiye: Turkish Thrace (without locality information) (Péricart, 1984, 2001)

Asian Türkiye: Çankırı, Diyarakır (Lodos et al., 1984; Bolu 2020; Yazıcı et al., 2022)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Central Asia and the Far East.

***Berytinus hirticornis nigrolineatus* (Jakovlev, 1903)**

European Türkiye: Turkish Thrace (without locality information) (Péricart, 2001b)

Asian Türkiye: Akşehir, Ankara, Diyarbakır, Hatay, Isparta, Karaman, Konya (Seidenstücker, 1957 as *Berytinus nigrolineatus*; Péricart, 1984; Matocq et al., 2014; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Bulgaria, Crete, Greece, Italy, Russia, Ukraine, European and Asian Türkiye, Afghanistan, Transcaucasia, Cyprus, Middle East, Central Asia.

***Berytinus hirticornis pilipes* (Puton, 1875)**

Asian Türkiye: Ankara (Kıyak, 2016b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Crete, France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain. North Africa: Algeria, Canary Islands, Morocco, Madeira, Tunisia. Asia: Asian Türkiye.

***Berytinus minor minor* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

European Türkiye: Turkish Thrace (without locality information) (Péricart, 1984, 2001)

Asian Türkiye: Nevşehir (Kıyak et al., 2004)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Iran, Russia. Extralimital: North America (Canada, USA).

Subgenus *Lizinus* Mulsant & Rey, 1870

***Berytinus consimilis* (Horváth, 1885)**

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Eskişehir, Sakarya (Horváth, 1905; Hoberlandt, 1956; Péricart, 1984; Önder et al., 2006)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and Southern Europe, Asian Türkiye, Georgia.

***Berytinus distinguendus* (Ferrari, 1874)**

European Türkiye: Turkish Thrace? (Péricart, 2001b)

Asian Türkiye: Bilecik, Burdur, Çanakkale, Elazığ, Gümüşhane, İzmir, Konya, Manisa, Niğde (Seidenstücker, 1957; Péricart, 1984; Çerçi et al., 2018)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian

Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Cyprus, Iran, Israel, Central Asia.

***Berytinus geniculatus* (Horváth, 1885)**

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Ankara, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Erzurum, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Konya, Niğde (Linnavuori, 1953; Péricart, 1984; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Kiyak, 2016a; Eser & Dursun, 2023b)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iraq, Israel?, Jordan.

***Berytinus montivagus* (Meyer-Dür, 1841)**

European Türkiye: Tekirdağ (Péricart, 1984; Josifov, 1986)

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bursa, Çanakkale, Denizli, Diyarbakır, İzmir, Manisa, Mersin, Şanlıurfa (Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Péricart, 1984; Lodos et al., 1984; Önder et al., 2006; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı, 2022b)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, North Africa, Transcaucasia, Middle East, Central Asia.

***Berytinus setipennis* (Saunders, 1876)**

Asian Türkiye: Aydın, Bitlis, Bursa, Muğla, Yalova (Péricart, 1984; Seidenstücker, 1960a)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Southern Europe, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan?, Israel.

***Berytinus signoreti* (Fieber, 1859)**

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Bursa (Horváth, 1883; Hoberlandt, 1956; Önder et al., 2006)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, Cyprus.

***Berytinus striola* (Ferrari, 1874)**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Bursa, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Mardin Muğla (Péricart, 1984; Matocq et al., 2014; Çerçi et al., 2018)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, North Africa, Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Georgia, Iraq, Israel, Lebanon, Syria.

Subfamily GAMPSCORINAE Southwood & Leston, 1959

Tribe GAMPSCORINI Southwood & Leston, 1959

Genus *Gampsocoris* Fuss, 1852

***Gampsocoris culicinus culicinus* Seidenstücker, 1948**

European Türkiye: Edirne (Hoberlandt, 1956; Josifov, 1986; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Dursun, 2016b)

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Gümüşhane (Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, European and Asian Türkiye, North Africa, Asian Kazakhstan, Kirgizia, Russia.

***Gampsocoris culicinus melitenus* Seidenstücker, 1965**

European Türkiye: Edirne? (Péricart, 1984).

Asian Türkiye: Malatya (Péricart, 1984).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: European Türkiye?, Ukraine. Asia: Asian Türkiye.

Note: Type locality of this subspecies Gündüs-Bey [=Gündüzbey] Malatya (Péricart, 2001b).

Note: The distributions of *G. culicinus melitenus*, which was described by Seidenstücker,

(1965) from Malatya in Anatolia and the nominate subspecies *G. culicinus culicinus* are not clear in European Türkiye. While giving the distribution of these two subspecies in the catalog [probably according to Péricart (1984)], Aukema (2018) showed *G. culicinus melitenus* in European Türkiye but did not give any record of *G. culicinus culicinus*. Péricart (1984) did not give the distributions of the subspecies of *Gampsocoris culicinus* separately, but showed them with different symbols on the map (he used the symbols “■, □” for *G. culicinus culicinus* and “●, ○” for *G. culicinus melitenus*. ■, ●: examples that the author has checked, □, ○: examples that the author has not checked). The record marked with the symbol “□” from Edirne by Péricart (1984) is the record given by Hoberlandt (1956) as *G. culicinus* (before Seidenstücker, (1965) described *G. culicinus melitenus*), and this record most likely belongs to the nominate subspecies, not to *G. culicinus melitenus*. *G. culicinus culicinus* was given from European Türkiye by Josifov (1986) and Fent & Dursun, (2016b), in addition to from Hoberlandt (1956).

***Gampsocoris enslini* Seidenstücker, 1953**

European Türkiye: Edirne (Seidenstücker, 1958).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Aydın, Mersin (Seidenstücker, 1953b; Hoberlandt, 1956; Péricart, 1984; Önder et al., 2006)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Balkans, European and Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Iran, Yemen.

Note: The type locality of this species is Taurus, Namrun (Mersin) (Péricart, 2001b).

***Gampsocoris punctipes pallidus* Hoberlandt, 1951**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Diyarbakır, Düzce Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman (Hoberlandt, 1956; Seidenstücker, 1965; Önder et al., 1981; Lodos et al., 1984; Péricart, 1984; Matocq et al., 2014; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Asia: Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Syria, Tadzhikistan, Uzbekistan.

***Gampsocoris punctipes punctipes* (Germar, 1822)**

European Türkiye: Edirne, Kırklareli (Şerban, 2010; Josifov, 1986; Fent & Dursun, 2016b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, North Africa, Transcaucasia, Israel, Lebanon, Saudi Arabia.

Subfamily METACANTHINAE Douglas & Scott, 1865

Tribe METACANTHINI Douglas & Scott, 1865

Genus *Metacanthus* A. Costa, 1843

Subgenus *Cardopostethus* Fieber, 1859

***Metacanthus annulosus* (Fieber, 1859)**

Asian Türkiye: Adıyaman, Ankara, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bingöl, Elazığ, Gümüşhane, Hatay, İzmir, Kastamonu, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Sinop, Zonguldak (Seidenstücker, 1960a as *Metacanthus breviceps*; Péricart, 1984; Morkel 2007; Matocq et al., 2014; Dursun, 2016)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Israel, Lebanon.

Subgenus *Metacanthus* A. Costa, 1843

***Metacanthus meridionalis* (A. Costa, 1843)**

European Türkiye: Edirne, Tekirdağ (Fent & Dursun, 2016b)

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Ankara, Balıkesir, Bursa, Bitlis, Çankırı, Hakkari, İzmir,

Manisa, Mardin (Horváth, 1883; Reuter, 1890; Péricart, 1984; Önder et al., 2006; Matocq et al., 2014; Dursun, 2016; Eser & Dursun, 2023b; Yazıcı et al., 2023)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, European and Asian Türkiye Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Yemen.

Tribe METATROPINI Henry, 1997

Genus *Metatropis* Fieber, 1859

Metatropis rufescens (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)

Asian Türkiye: Rize (Kment & Fent, 2012)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Georgia, Israel?, Japan, Russia.

Family BLISSIDAE Stål, 1862

Subfamily BLISSINAE Stål, 1862

Genus *Blissus* Burmeister, 1835

Blissus hirtulus Burmeister, 1835

Asian Türkiye: Hatay (Çerçi et al., 2024)

Distribution in Palaearctic: North Africa, Arab Emirates, China (SE), Japan, Saudi Arabia, Yemen. Extralimital: Borneo, India and tropical Africa (Chad, Ethiopia, Sudan).

Blissus putoni Jakovlev, 1875

Asian Türkiye: İzmir (Péricart, 1999a),

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: European Kazakhstan, Greece, Russia. Asia: Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, China.

Genus *Dimorphopterus* Stål, 1872

Dimorphopterus blissoides (Baerensprung, 1859)

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Çanakkale Province: Gelibolu–Yolağzı village (Uzunhızarlı Dam) 28.05.2019, 1 ♀; Edirne Province: Uzunköprü–Çöpköy, 16.05.2016, 1 ♀; İpsala road (20. km) 08.06.2016, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; Keşan–Mecidiye, 22.07.2016, 1 ♀, 3 ♂♂, 10 nymphs. İstanbul Province: Silivri–Fenerköy, 19.08.2015, 2 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, 5 nymphs; Kırklareli Province: Lüleburgaz–Evrensekiz, 14.05.2016, 15 ♀♀, 21 ♂♂; Center–Kavaklı, 09.06.2016, 8 ♀♀, 27 ♂♂.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Elazığ, Mersin (Linnavuori, 1953; Péricart, 1999a; Çerçi et al., 2018; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Eastern and southern Europe, Armenia, Asian Türkiye Azerbaijan, Israel, Iraq.

Dimorphopterus doriae (Ferrari, 1874)

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Enez (Karagöl), 01.09.2015, 1 ♀; Süloğlu (Dam), 15.05.2016, 1 ♂; Meriç–Akıncılar road, 19.05.2016, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; Kırklareli Province: Center–Üsküp, 22.08.2015, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Aksaray, Amasya, Bolu İzmir, Niğde, Tokat, Yalova (Reuter, 1890; Lodos et al., 1999 as *Blissus doriai*; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 1983, 2006 as *Blissus doriae*; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Eastern and southern Europe, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Iran, Syria.

Dimorphopterus spinolae (Signoret, 1857)

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Uzunköprü–Kavacık, 14.07.2016, 1 ♂, 6 nymphs; İstanbul Province: Silivri–Fenerköy, 19.08.2015, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Konya, Sinop, Sivas (Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Iran, Japan?, Central Asia.

Genus *Ischnodemus* Fieber, 1837

***Ischnodemus caspius* Jakovlev, 1871**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Çanakkale Province: Gelibolu–Yolağzı village (Uzunhızarlı Dam), 28.05.2019, 15 ♀♀, 12 ♂♂, Edirne Province: Enez (Karagöl), 01.09.2015, 1 ♀; Süloğlu (Dam), 15.05.2016, 1 ♂; Meriç–Akıncılar road, 19.05.2016, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; Kırklareli Province: Center–Üsküp, 22.08.2015, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Diyarbakır, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş (Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Fent et al., 2022; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Balkans, Egypt. Afghanistan, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia.

***Ischnodemus genei* (Spinola, 1837)**

Asian Türkiye: Artvin, Bursa, Mardin (Horváth, 1883; Reuter, 1895; Péricart, 1999a; Matocq et al., 2014).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Southern Europe North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Iraq, Israel.

***Ischnodemus sabuleti* (Fallén, 1826)**

Material examined: İstanbul Province: Between Çatalca–İhsaniye, 11.06.2016, 62 ♀♀, 65 ♂♂; Hisarbeyli, 13.06.2016, 2 ♂♂; Akalan Bridge, 14.06.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Silivri–between Danamandıra–Küçüksinekli, 13.06.2016, 6 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂; Kırklareli Province: Pehlivan köyü, 19.06.2015, 11 ♀♀, 9 ♂♂; Tekirdağ Province: Hayrabolu–Danışment, 18.06.2015, 1 ♂; between Danışment–Çerkezmüşellim, 18.06.2015, 1 ♂; between Saray–Safaalan, 18.08.2015, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: İstanbul (Horváth, 1918; Önder *et al.*, 2006)

Asian Türkiye: Bursa, Hatay, Mersin (Horváth, 1883, 1901; Önder *et al.*, 2006).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Central Asia, Syria.

***Ischnodemus suturalis* Horváth, 1883**

European Türkiye: Turkish Thrace (Protić 1987; Péricart, 1999a).

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Bursa, Gaziantep, İzmir, Mardin, Osmaniye (Horváth, 1883; Reuter, 1885; Seidenstücker, 1958; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder *et al.*, 2006; Kıyak & Akar, 2010).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: European Türkiye, Serbia. Asia: Asian Türkiye, Israel, Syria.

Note: The type locality of this species is Brussa [=Bursa] (Péricart, 2001a).

Family CYMIDAE Baerensprung, 1860

Subfamily CYMINAE Baerensprung, 1860

Tribe CYMINI Baerensprung, 1868

Genus *Cymodema* Spinola, 1837

***Cymodema tabida tabida* Spinola, 1837**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Uzunköprü–Çavuşlu,

14.07.2016, 1 ♂; Istanbul Province: Between Çatalca-İhsaniye, 11.06.2016, 34 ♀♀, 47 ♂♂, 10 nymphs; Çatalca-Yazlık, 12.06.2016, 1 ♂; Hisarbeyli, 13.06.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Akalan Bridge, 14.06.2016, 1 ♂; Tekirdağ Province: Between Saray-Safaalan, 11.06.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Çorlu-next to the Unilever, 17.07.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Muratlı-Hanoğlu, 17.07.2016, 44 ♀♀, 41 ♂♂, 10 nymphs.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Mersin (Péricart, 1999a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Israel. Extralimital: Chad, Sudan.

Genus *Cymus* Hahn, 1832

***Cymus aurescens* Distant, 1883**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Tekirdağ Province: Şarköy-Yayaköy, 17.08.2020, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: İstanbul (Belgrad Forest) (Péricart, 1999a).

Asian Türkiye: Adana (Taurus Montains), Konya (Péricart, 1999a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, Central Asia, China (NE), Russia.

***Cymus claviculus* (Fallén, 1807)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Center, 01.07.2015, 1 ♂; Uzunköprü-Kavacık, 14.07.2016, 2 ♀♀; Kırklareli Province: Center-Çağlayık, 15.08.2015, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Edirne (Josifov, 1986; Péricart, 1999a).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Bartın, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kocaeli, Konya, Mersin, Muğla, Sakarya, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1901; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939; Hoberlandt, 1956; Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1978, 1984, 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 1981, 2006; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yazıcı et al., 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia.

***Cymus glandicolor* Hahn, 1832**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Center-Uzgaç, 01.07.2015, 2 ♀♀, 9 ♂♂; Istanbul Province: Çatalca-İhsaniye, 11.06.2016, 4 ♂♂; Akalan Bridge, 14.06.2016, 2 ♂♂.

European Türkiye: İstanbul (Horváth, 1918).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Bartın, Bursa, Erzurum, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırşehir, Kocaeli, Kütahya, Osmaniye, Yalova, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1901; Kiritshenko, 1918; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, Central Asia, China, Iran, Japan, Korea, Russia.

***Cymus gracilicornis* Vidal, 1940**

Asian Türkiye: Kahramanmaraş, Mersin (Péricart, 1999a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East. Extralimital: Cabo Verde Island; Sudan.

***Cymus melanocephalus* Fieber, 1861**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Enez (Dalyan Lake), 31.08.2015, 50 ♀♀, 38 ♂♂; Karagöl, 01.09.2015, 7 ♀♀, 9 ♂♂; Süloğlu (Dam),

15.05.2016, 1 ♀; Uzunköprü-Çöpköy, 16.05.2016, 13 ♀♀, 13 ♂♂; 08.06.2016, 2 ♀♀; Ömerbey, 16.05.2016, 2 ♀♀; Meriç-Olacak village, 19.05.2016, 1 ♂; Keşan-Mecidiye, 22.07.2016, 1 ♀; Kocahıdır, 22.07.2016, 12 ♀♀, 13 ♂♂; Center-Balkan Campus, 16.05.2017, 5 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; 03.08.2018, 4 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; **İstanbul Province:** Çatalca, 18.08.2015, 2 ♂♂; Danamandıra, 11.06.2016, 55 ♀♀, 38 ♂♂; Between Çatalca-İhsaniye, 11.06.2016, 15 ♀♀, 15 ♂♂; Hisarbeyli, 13.06.2016, 7 ♀♀, 9 ♂♂; Akalan Bridge, 14.06.2016, 4 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂; Arnavutköy road, 12.06.2016, 2 ♀♀; Silivri-between Danamandıra-Küçüksinekli, 13.06.2016, 33 ♀♀, 26 ♂♂; **Kırklareli Province:** Kofçaz-Kadıköy, 17.06.2015, 1 ♀; Demirköy-Sislioba, 24.06.2015, 2 ♂♂; İğneada, 24.06.2015, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; between Hamdibey-Yeşilce, 26.06.2015, 1 ♂; Center-Üsküpdere, 16.06.2016, 1 ♂; Vize-Doğanca, 16.07.2016, 82 ♀♀, 80 ♂♂; **Tekirdağ Province:** Between Saray-Safaalan, 11.06.2016, 10 ♀♀, 11 ♂♂; Çorlu-next to the Unilever, 17.07.2016, 10 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; Ergene-Esenler, 17.07.2016, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Muratlı-Balıhoca, 16.07.2016, 10 ♀♀, 14 ♂♂; Hanoğlu, 17.07.2016, 1 ♀; Saray-Çaylaköy, 18.07.2016, 43 ♀♀, 46 ♂♂; Malkara-Izgar village, 22.06.2017, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Ahmetpaşaköy, 22.06.2017, 6 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂.

European Türkiye: Çanakkale, Edirne, İstanbul (Horváth, 1918; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978; Josifov, 1986; Önder et al., 1984, 2006; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Bartın, Bayburt, Bolu Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Karabük, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Kocaeli, Konya, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Sinop, Sivas, Tunceli, Yalova, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1901; Hoberlandt, 1956; Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2022; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Özgen et al., 2021a; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaeartic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia.

***Cymus turcicus* Matocq, 2000**

Asian Türkiye: Konya (Beyşehir) (Matocq, 2000)

Distribution in Palaeartic: Asia: AsianTürkiye.

Note: The type locality of this species is Beyşehir (Konya) (Péricart, 2001a). This species is endemic to Anatolia (Dursun & Fent, 2017).

Family GEOCORIDAE Baerensprung, 1860

Subfamily BLEDIONOTINAE Reuter, 1878

Tribe BLEDIONOTINI Reuter, 1878

Genus *Bledionotus* Reuter, 1878

***Bledionotus systellonotoides* Reuter, 1878**

Asian Türkiye: Bursa (Seidenstücker, 1960a; Péricart, 1999b)

Distribution in Palaeartic: Asia: Afghanistan, Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Iraq, Syria, Tadzhikistan.

Subfamily GEOCORINAE Dahlbom, 1851

Genus *Geocoris* Falén, 1814

Subgenus *Eilatus* Linnavuori, 1972

***Geocoris chloroticus* Puton, 1888**

Asian Türkiye: Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Kilis, Mersin (Lodos et al., 1999)

Distribution in Palaeartic: Portugal, Spain, Greece. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia. Extralimal: Cabo Verde Is, India, Sudan.

Subgenus *Geocoris* Fallén, 1814***Geocoris ater* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Material examined: **EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE:** Edirne Province: Enez Çıkışı, 03.09.2015, 1 ♂; Süloğlu (Dam), 15.05.2016, 1 ♂; Center-Balkan Campus, 08.05.2017 2 ♀♀, 28.06.2017, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Kırklareli Province: Deveçatağı, 04.06.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Edirne (Fent & Okyar, 2022).

Asian Türkiye: Afyonkarahisar, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Çorum, Denizli, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Sinop, Yozgat (Puton & Noualhier, 1895, as *Geocoris ater* var. *albipennis* and var. *ataenius*; Lodos et al., 1978, as *G. ater* var. *pallescens*, 1999; Tezcan & Önder, 2003; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Çakır & Önder, 1990; Kaya & Hıncal, 1991; Péricart, 1999a; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Yılmaz & Dursun, 2022; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yazıcı et al., 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia, Afghanistan, Far East.

***Geocoris grylloides* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Diyarbakır, Isparta, Mardin, Muş (Wagner, 1959; Çakır & Önder, 1990; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Yılmaz & Dursun, 2022).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, Iran, Central Asia, Far East.

***Geocoris lapponicus* Zetterstedt, 1838**

Asian Türkiye: Artvin, Kayseri (Erciyes Mountain) (Kerzhner 1979; Péricart, 1999a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, China, Georgia, Mongolia, Russia.

***Geocoris lineola lineola* (Rambur, 1839)**

Material examined: **EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE:** İstanbul Province: Silivri-Küçüksinekli, 15.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂; Kırklareli Province: Center-Çukurpınar, 21.05.2016, 1 ♂; Tekirdağ Province: Muratlı-Ballıhoca, 16.07.2016, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bolu Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Gaziantep, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri (Aladağlar Mts.), Osmaniye, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla (Kiritshenko, 1918; Hoberlandt, 1956 as *Geocoris lineola* and *G. lineola* var. *distinctus*; Aysev, 1974; Çağatay, 1989a; Çakır & Önder, 1990; Péricart, 1999a; Kıyak, 2000; Önder et al., 2006; Öncül-Abacıgil et al., 2010; Şerban, 2010; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Yazıcı, 2022b; Yılmaz & Dursun, 2022; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Balkans, southern Europe, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East.

***Geocoris megacephalus* (Rossi, 1790)**

Material examined: **EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE:** Edirne Province: Uzunköprü road, 27.08.2015, 3 ♀♀; Çavuşlu, 14.07.2016, 1 ♀; Süloğlu (Dam), 15.05.2016, 1 ♀; Keşan-Mecidiye, 22.07.2016, 1 ♀; Center-Balkan Campus, 08.05.2017, 1 ♀; İstanbul Province: Silivri-Küçüksinekli, 15.06.2016, 1 ♀; Tekirdağ Province: Between Saray-Safaalan, 18.08.2015, 1 ♂; Çorlu-next to the Unilever, 17.07.2016, 2 ♀♀.

European Türkiye: Edirne, Tekirdağ (Çakır & Önder, 1990; Fent & Okyar, 2022).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kayseri, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Siirt, Şanlıurfa, Uşak (Hoberlandt, 1956; Aysev, 1974; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Çağatay, 1989a; Çakır & Önder, 1990; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Öncül-Abacıgil et al., 2010; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Yazıcı, 2019; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Yılmaz & Dursun, 2022; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Afghanistan, Central Asia.

***Geocoris pallidipennis pallidipennis* (A. Costa, 1843)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Süloğlu (Dam), 15.05.2016, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Amasya, Ankara, Batman, Bursa, Diyarbakır, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Kilis, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Niğde, Şanlıurfa, Tunceli, Van (Hoberlandt, 1956, *G. pallidipennis* and *G. pallidipennis* var. *semipunctatus*), Çağatay, 1989a; Çakır & Önder, 1990; Büyük & Özpınar, 1999; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Tezcan & Önder, 2003; Koçak & Kemal, 2012; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Kemal & Koçak, 2018; Önder et al., 2006; Özgen 2021; Yılmaz & Dursun, 2022).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, North Africa, Middle East, Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, China, Korea. Extralimital: India, Pakistan.

***Geocoris phaeopterus* (Germar, 1838)**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Hatay, Karaman, Mardin, Şanlıurfa (Péricart, 1999a; Matocq et al., 2014; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: France, Italy, Spain. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East. Extralimital: Pakistan, South Africa, Cabo Verde Isl.

***Geocoris pubescens* (Jakovlev, 1871)**

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Ankara, Elazığ, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kastamonu, Malatya, Sinop (Péricart, 1999a; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Kıyak, 2016a; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Çerçi et al., 2022; Yılmaz & Dursun, 2022; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Balkans, Russia, Ukraine, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Middle East. Extralimital: Cabo Verde Is, Sudan.

Subgenus *Piocoris* Stål, 1872

***Geocoris erythrocephalus* (Lepelletier & Serville, 1825)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Canakkale Province: Ilgardere, 17.05.2016, 1 ♀; Edirne Province: Center-Uzgaç, 01.07.2015, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Keşan-Koru Mountains (Küçükyerlisu), 18.05.2016, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Kocahıdır, 22.07.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Mecidiye, 22.07.2016, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, Karahisar, 24.07.2016, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Uzunköprü-Kavacık, 14.07.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Çavuşlu, 14.07.2016, 6 ♀♀, 7 ♂♂; Mestanlar, 14.07.2016, 1 ♂; Center-Balkan Campus, 08.05.2017 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; 21.06.2018, 1 ♀; 29.06.2018, 1 ♀; Kırklareli Province: Center-Çağlayık, 15.08.2015, 1 ♀; Üsküp, 21.05.2016, 1 ♂; Beypınar, 06.06.2016; 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Demirköy-Boztaş, 25.06.2015, 1 ♂; Between Hamdibey-Yeşilce, 26.06.2015, 1 ♀; Pınarhisar, 16.06.2016, 3 ♀♀; Lüleburgaz-Kırıkköy, 15.07.2016, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; İstanbul Province: Çatalca-Binkılıç, 18.08.2015, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Hisarbeyli, 13.06.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Tekirdağ Province: Center-Mermer, 20.08.2015, 11 ♀♀, 10 ♂♂; Uçmakdere, 20.08.2015, 1 ♀; Şarköy, 21.08.2015, 1 ♀; Çorlu-next to the Unilever, 17.07.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Muratlı-Balıhoca, 16.07.2016, 8 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂; Hanoğlu, 17.07.2016, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Çanakkale, Edirne, İstanbul, Tekirdağ (Fahringer, 1922; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978, as *Piocoris erythrocephalus*; Josifov, 1986; Çakır & Önder, 1990; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006, as *P. erythrocephalus*; Fent & Aktaç, 2008; Fent & Okyar, 2022).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bolu Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Gümüşhane, Hakkari, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Siirt, Sinop, Şanlıurfa, Trabzon, Osmaniye, Uşak, Yalova, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1901, 1905; Puton, 1892; Escherich, 1897; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1959, 1966; Linnavuori, 1965; Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Çağatay, 1989a; Çakır & Önder, 1990; Öz Saraç & Kıyak 2001; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 1983, 2006, as *Piocoris erythrocephalus*; Kıyak, 1990, 1993, 2000, 2016a; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Beyaz & Tezcan, 2002; Gençer et al., 2004; Kıyak et al., 2004; Kaplan 2007; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Şerban, 2010; Sert et al., 2013; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2022; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Yazıcı, 2019, 2022a, b; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Çerçi et al., 2018, 2022; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asia: Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Transcaucasia.

***Geocoris luridus* (Fieber, 1844)**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Ankara, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kilis, Konya, Mardin, Mersin, Osmaniye, Şanlıurfa (Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Seidenstücker, 1958, as *Piocoris luridus*; Çağatay, 1989a; Çakır & Önder, 1990; Büyük & Özpınar, 1999; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006, as *P. luridus*; Matocq et al., 2014; Çerçi et al., 2018; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Özgen et al., 2021c; Sabuncu et al., 2021; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia, Extralimital: Ethiopia, Sudan.

***Geocoris nebulosus* (Montandon, 1907)**

Asian Türkiye: Adana (Péricart, 1999a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Extralimital: Djibouti, Sudan.

***Geocoris putonianus* Bergroth, 1892**

Asian Türkiye: Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Mardin, Van (Matocq et al., 2014; Kemal & Koçak, 2018; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Özgen et al., 2021c).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Asia: Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye Iran, Kirgizia, Tadzhikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan.

Subfamily HENESTARINAE Douglas & Scott, 1865

Genus *Engistus* Fieber, 1844

***Engistus exsanguis exsanguis* Stål, 1872**

Asian Türkiye: Karaman (Çerçi & Koçak, 2017)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Greece, Russia (ST) Spain, Ukraine. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia, Extralimital: Cabo Verde Is, Mauritania, W Pakistan, Sudan.

***Engistus salinus* (Jakovlev, 1874)**

Asian Türkiye: Aksaray, Çorum (Lodos et al., 1999; Çerçi et al., 2022).

Distribution in Palaearctic: European Kazakhstan, Greece, Russia, Ukraine, Asiaan Türkiye, Central Asia, China (NO), Iran, Mongolia.

Genus *Henestaris* Spinola, 1837

Henestaris halophilus (Burmeister, 1835)

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Enez (Karagöl) 01.09.2015, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Uzunköprü-Kavacık, 14.07.2016, 1 ♂; Tekirdağ Province: Between Saray-Safaalan, 18.08.2015, 1 ♀; Şarköy, 21.08.2015, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Antalya, Çanakkale (Gökçeada) Erzurum, Konya, Hatay, Mersin (Kiritshenko, 1924 as *H. cremeus*; Hoberlandt, 1956 as *H. cremeus*; Seidenstücker, 1958 as *H. cremeus*; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Morocco, Asian Türkiye, Central Asia, China (NE NW), Iran, Syria, Mongolia, Russia.

Henestaris kareli Hoberlandt, 1956

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Çorum, Konya, Yozgat (Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Asia: Asian Türkiye.

Note: The type locality of this species is Mogan Gölü (Ankara) (Péricart, 2001a). This species is endemic to Anatolia (Dursun & Fent, 2017).

Henestaris laticeps laticeps (Curtis, 1836)

European Türkiye: Tekirdağ (Wagner, 1966 as *H. curtulus*)

Asian Türkiye: Antalya, Çanakkale (Bozcaada), Çankırı, Hatay, İzmir, Muğla (Linnavuori, 1953; Seidenstücker, 1958 as *Henestaris curtulus*; Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Fent, 2011; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Yazıcı, 2022b; Yazıcı et al., 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Iraq, Syria. Extralimital: Djibouti!

Family HETEROGASTRIDAE Stål, 1872

Subfamily HETEROGASTRINAE Stål, 1872

Genus *Heterogaster* Schilling, 1829

Heterogaster affinis Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Bursa, Çankırı, Elazığ, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Nevşehir, Niğde (Aladağlar Mts.), Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883; Hoberlandt, 1956; Yiğit & Uygun, 1982; Çağatay, 1989b; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Kıyak, 2000; Kıyak et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022b; Yazıcı et al., 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Iran, Syria, Central Asia.

Heterogaster artemisiae Schilling, 1829

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Meriç-Kadıondurma, 20.05.2016, 1 ♀; Kırklareli Province: Center-Beypınar, 22.05.2016; 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: Edirne (Hoberlandt, 1956; Josifov, 1986).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Düzce, Erzurum, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Mersin, Niğde, (Aladağlar Mts.), Osmaniye (Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Hoberlandt, 1956; Çağatay, 1989b, Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart,

1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Yazıcı, 2022b; Eser & Dursun, 2023b; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Iran, Iraq, Central Asia, China.

***Heterogaster cathariae* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Çankırı, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Gümüşhane, Hatay, İzmir, Karaman, Kars, Mersin (Puton & Noualhier, 1895 as *H. cathariae* var. *bicolor*; Kiritshenko, 1918; Hoberlandt, 1956; Çağatay, 1989b; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2023; Çerçi et al., 2018, 2022; Yazıcı, 2022b; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Iran, Cyprus, Central Asia, China.

***Heterogaster urticae* (Fabricius, 1775)**

European Türkiye: Turkish Thrace (without locality information) (Josifov, 1986).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Çankırı, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Osmaniye, Samsun, Trabzon, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1905; Hoberlandt, 1956; Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Yiğit & Uygun, 1982; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Çağatay, 1989b; Tezcan & Önder, 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Öncül-Abacıgil et al., 2010; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Çıtıkkaya et al., 2015; Kıyak, 2016a; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2023; Yazıcı, 2022b; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia. Extralimital (introduced): New Zealand.

Genus *Platyplax* Fieber, 1860

***Platyplax inermis* (Rambur, 1839)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: İstanbul Province: Çatalca-Yazlık, 12.06.2016, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Balıkesir, Bursa, Çanakkale, İzmir, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Mersin (Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Çağatay, 1989b; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı, 2022b; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Israel, Yemen. Extralimital: Ethiopia.

***Platyplax salviae* (Schilling, 1829)**

Material examined: ASIAN TÜRKİYE: Giresun Province: Alucra-Arda village, 17.05.2006, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Sivas Province: Koyulhisar-Karaağaç, 2 ♂♂.

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Antalya, Bursa, Erzurum, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Mersin (Horváth, 1883, as *Platyplax salviae* var. *inermis*, 1905; Hoberlandt, 1956; Çağatay, 1989b; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Algeria, Morocco, Asian Central Asia. Iran, Israel, Afghanistan, China.

Family LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829

Subfamily LYGAEINAE Schilling, 1829

Genus *Apterola* Mulsant & Rey, 1866

Subgenus *Apterola* Mulsant & Rey, 1866***Apterola kuenckeli kuenckeli* Mulsant & Rey, 1866**

Asian Türkiye: Mersin, Tokat (Péricart, 1999a; Lodos et al., 1999, as *Apterola pedestris*; Önder et al., 2006, as *A. pedestris*)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Bulgaria, France, Greece, Italy, Malta, Macedonia, Spain. North Africa: Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia. Asia: Asian Türkiye.

***Apterola kuenckeli rubicunda* (Stål, 1872)**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Elazığ, Gaziantep, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş (Puton & Noualhier, 1895 as *Apterola rubicunda*; Hoberlandt, 1956, as *A. rubicunda*; Lodos et al., 1999, as *A. rubicunda*; Önder et al., 2006, as *A. rubicunda* Çerçi et al., 2018).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Asia: Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Iran, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Syria.

***Apterola lownii* (Saunders, 1876)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Center-Uzgaç, 01.07.2015, 5 ♀♀, 12 ♂♂; 08.07.2015, 25 ♀♀, 22 ♂♂; Kırköy, 04.07.2015, 1 ♂; Lalapaşa-Ömeroba, 15.07.2015, 1 ♀; Keşan Korumaları (Küçükyerlisu), 18.05.2016, 1 ♀; Kırklareli Province: Pınarhisar (Mahya Hill), 30.06.2015, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Edirne (Hoberlandt, 1956; Josifov, 1986; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Amasya, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kayseri, Konya, Malatya, Mardin, Mersin, Niğde (Aladağlar Mts.) (Horváth, 1898, 1905; Hoberlandt, 1956; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Kiyak & Özdamar 2017; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Bulgaria, European Türkiye, Greece, Macedonia. Asia: Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Kirgizia, Syria, Tadzhikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan.

Genus *Arocatus* Spinola, 1837***Arocatus longiceps* Stål, 1872**

Material examined: Edirne Province: Uzunköprü-Kavacık, 14.07.2016, 1 ♂; Center, 13.04.2018, 1 ♀; Tekirdağ Province: Center-Mermer, 20.08.2015, 10 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Uçmakdere, 20.08.2015, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Çanakkale, Edirne, İstanbul, Tekirdağ (Lodos et al., 1978; Önder et al., 1984, 2006; Péricart, 1999a; Fent & Aktaş, 2008).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Bartın, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Denizli, Mersin, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Mersin, Muğla, Samsun, Uşak, Zonguldak (Linnavuori, 1965; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Çağatay, 1995; Péricart, 1999a; Tezcan & Önder, 1999; Gao et al., 2013; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Madeira Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Cyprus, Iran, Israel.

***Arocatus melanocephalus* (Fabricius, 1798)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Uzunköprü-Saçlımüsellim, 13.06.2015, 5 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂; Center-Balkan Campus, 25.07.2018, 1 ♂; 20.08.2019, 6 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; 10.10.2018, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: Edirne, İstanbul, Tekirdağ (Çağatay, 1995; Péricart, 1999a; Fent & Aktaş, 2008).

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Aydın, Denizli, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Manisa,

Muğla, Sinop, Zonguldak (Escherich, 1897; Hoberlandt, 1956; Çağatay, 1995; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia China, Iran.

***Arocatus roeselii* (Schilling, 1829)**

Material examined: **EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE:** Edirne Province: Center-Balkan Campus, 29.06.2018, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Bursa (Reuter, 1890; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Algeria, Tunisia North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Asian Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Syria.

Genus *Caenocoris* Fieber, 1860

***Caenocoris nerii* (Germar, 1847)**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Antalya, Aydın, Hatay, İzmir, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla (Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Seidenstücker, 1958; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Çağatay, 1995; Péricart, 1999a; Tezcan & Önder, 2003; Önder et al., 2006; Şerban, 2010; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Çıtırıkaya et al., 2015)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, China (SE), Georgia, Extralimital: Oriental Region (India, Pakistan), tropical Africa.

Genus *Graptostethus* Stål, 1868

***Graptostethus servus servus* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bursa, İzmir, Manisa (Bozdağlar), Muğla (Reuter, 1890 as *Graptostethus servus* var. *maculicollis*; Çağatay, 1995; Péricart, 1999a, Önder et al., 2006; Öncül-Abacıgil et al., 2010; Tezcan et al., 2010).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Far East.

Genus *Horvathiolus* Josifov, 1965

***Horvathiolus kiritshenkoi kiritshenkoi* (Horváth, 1916)**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Antalya, Gaziantep (Péricart, 1999a; Çerçi & Tezcan, 2020).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Asia: Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Iran.

***Horvathiolus superbus* (Pollich, 1781)**

Material examined: Edirne Province: Keşan Koru Mountains (Küçükyerlisu), 18.05.2016, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂. Sivas Province: Akıncılar, Sevindik village 21.09.2007, 1 ♀; Suşehri-Solak, 16.05.2007, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: Edirne (Josifov, 1986; Fent & Aktaş, 2008).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bolu Çankırı, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, İzmir, Karaman, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kilis, Konya, Mersin, Niğde, Uşak, Van (Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Horváth, 1905; Kiritshenko, 1918; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939; Hoberlandt, 1956; Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Kaya & Hıncal, 1991; Çağatay, 1995; Péricart, 1999a; Tezcan & Önder, 1999; Kıyak, 1993, 2000; Önder et al., 2006; Öncül-Abacıgil et al., 2010; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Dursun, 2016; Kemal & Koçak, 2018; Özgen & Dioli, 2019; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yazıcı et al., 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Canary Islands, Madeira Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia, China.

Note: Puton & Noualhier (1895), Horváth (1905), Kiritshenko, (1918), Gadeau de Kerville (1939), Lodos et al. (1978, 1999) Kıyak (1993, 2000), Önder et al. (2006) gave this species as *Melanocoryphus superbis* and Hoberlandt (1956) gave as *M. superbis* and *M. superbis* var. *erythropus*.

***Horvathiolus syriacus* (Reuter, 1885)**

Material examined. ASIAN TÜRKİYE: Kahramanmaraş Province: Afşin, 21.09.2008, 2 ♀♀; Sivas Province: Suşehri-Yalnıztepe, 16.05.2006, 1 ♀;

European Türkiye: Edirne, İstanbul (Horváth, 1916, 1918; Josifov, 1986; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Aktaş, 2008).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Antalya, Diyarbakır, İstanbul, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Konya, Mersin, Niğde (Horváth, 1916, as *Melanocoryphus syriacus*; Hoberlandt, 1956, as *M. syriacus*; Wagner, 1959 as *M. syriacus*; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006 as *M. syriacus*; Çerçi et al., 2022; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Bulgaria, Crete, European and Asian Türkiye, Greece, Italy, Romania, Russia (ST), Spain, North Africa, Middle East, Central Asia.

Genus *Lygaeosoma* Spinola, 1837

***Lygaeosoma anatolicum* Seidenstücker, 1960**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Uzunköprü, 15.07.2015, 12 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Bingöl, Çankırı, Erzurum, Hatay, Kırkkale, Konya, Manisa, Mersin (Seidenstücker, 1960b; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Tezcan & Önder, 2003; Önder et al., 2006; Çerçi et al., 2022; Eser & Dursun, 2023a; Yazıcı et al., 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern and southern Europe, Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Middle East.

Note: The type locality of this species is Antakya– Harbiye (Hatay) (Péricart, 2001a).

***Lygaeosoma angulare* Reuter, 1885**

Asian Türkiye: Akşehir, Amasya, Bingöl, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Konya, Manisa (Seidenstücker, 1957; Péricart, 1999a; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Bulgaria, Greece, Macedonia. Asia: Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Lebanon.

***Lygaeosoma sardeum sardeum* Spinola, 1837**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Enez (Dalyan Lake), 31.08.2015, 1 ♀; Hisarlı, 31.08.2015, 1 ♀; Sülüoğlu (Dam), 15.05.2016, 1 ♂; Uzunköprü–Çöpköy, 16.05.2016, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Center–Balkan Campus, 08.05.2017, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; 16.05.2017, 1 ♂; 21.06.2018, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Keşan–Koru Mountains, 21.07.2016, 1 ♂; Kırklareli Province: Center–Üsküp, 22.08.2015, 1 ♀; Pınarhisar, 16.06.2016, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Bingöl, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırkkale, Kırşehir, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Mersin, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Tokat, Yozgat (Horváth, 1883; Reuter, 1890; Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1984, 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Tezcan & Önder, 1999; Kıyak, 2000; Kıyak et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Şerban, 2010; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Çerçi et al., 2018; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yazıcı, 2022b; Yazıcı et al., 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian

Türkiye, Iran, Syria, Middle East, Central Asia.

Note: Horváth, 1883, Gadeau de Kerville (1939), Puton & Noualhier (1895), Lodost et al (1984), Hoberlandt (1956), Lodos et al. (1999), Kiyak et al. (2004) and Önder et al. (2006) mentioned this species as *L. reticulatum*.

***Lygaeosoma sardeum erythropterum* (Puton, 1876)**

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Antalya, Düzce, Hatay, İzmir, Kastamonu, Mersin, Kahramanmaraş, Sakarya, Tokat (Reuter, 1890 as *Lygaeosoma reticulatum* var. *erythropterum*; Puton, 1892, as *L. reticulatum* var. *erythropterum*; Puton & Noualhier, 1895 as *L. reticulatum* var. *erythropterum*; Hoberlandt, 1956 as *L. reticulatum* var. Fent & Dursun, 2016a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Crete, Greece, Macedonia, Spain. North Africa: Morocco. Asia: Asian Türkiye, Cyprus.

***Lygaeosoma sibiricum* Seidenstücker, 1962**

Asian Türkiye: Ankara (Kızılcahamam), Kayseri (Erciyes Mountain) Péricart (1999a),

Distribution in Palaearctic: Eastern Europe, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, China, Iran, Mongolia, Russia, Turkmenistan.

Genus *Lygaeus* Fabricius, 1794

***Lygaeus creticus* Lucas, 1854**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Gaziantep, Hakkari, Hatay, Isparta, İzmir, Karaman, Kırıkkale, Konya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Niğde (Aladağlar Mts.), Yalova (Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Horváth, 1901; Seidenstücker, 1958; Çağatay, 1995, Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Yiğit & Uygun, 1982; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Péricart, 1999a; Öncül-Abacıgil et al., 2010; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Matocq et al, 2014; Çitirikkaya et al, 2015; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Balkans, southern Europe, Libya. Asian Türkiye, Middle East

***Lygaeus equestris* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Uzunköprü-Saçlımüsellim, 13.06.2015, 1 ♂; Uzunköprü road, 27.08.2015, 8 ♀♀; Center-Uzgaç, 01.07.2015, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Balkan Campus, 21.06.2018, 1 ♀; 01.07.2018, 1 ♂; Süloğlu-Büyük Gerdelli village, 05.07.2015, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; Keşan-Koru Mountains (Küçükyerlisu), 18.05.2016, 1 ♂; Kırklareli Province: Center-Çağlayık, 15.08.2015, 2 ♀♀; Demirköy-Sislioba, 24.06.2015, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; İğneada, 24.06.2015, 1 ♀; Pınarhisar, 16.06.2016, 1 ♀; İstanbul Province: Çatalca-İhsaniye, 18.08.2015, 1 ♀. **ASIAN TÜRKİYE:** Sinop Province: İnceburun, 31.07.2007, 1 ♂.; Sivas Province: Suşehri-Yalnıztepe, 16.05.2006, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Çanakkale, Edirne, İstanbul, Kırklareli, Tekirdağ (Fahringer, 1922; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978; Josifov, 1986; Çağatay, 1995; Fent & Aktaç, 2008; Yazıcı et al., 2015).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bingöl, Bolu Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Hakkari, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul (Büyükkada), İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kilis, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Rize, Sinop, Sivas, Trabzon, Tunceli, Uşak, Van, Yozgat (Horváth, 1883, 1901, 1905, 1919; Puton, 1892; Escherich, 1897; Kiritshenko, 1918, 1924; Fahringer, 1922; A. F. de Seabra 1926; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1959, 1966; Linnavuori,

1965; Tuatay et al. 1967; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Altınayar 1981; Yiğit & Uygun, 1982; Önder et al., 1983, 1984, 2006; Özbek & Alaoğlu, 1987; Kiyak, 1990, 1993, 2000, 2016a; Kaya & Hıncal, 1991; Çağlar, 1992; Özbek et al., 1996; Çağatay, 1995; Péricart, 1999a; 2016; Öz Saraç & Kiyak 2001; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Tezcan & Önder, 1999, 2003; Gençer et al., 2004; Kiyak et al., 2004; Kiyak & Akar, 2010; Şerban, 2010; Sert & Kabalak, 2010; Fent, 2011; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Koçak & Kemal, 2012; Sert et al., 2013; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2022; Küçükbasmacı & Kiyak, 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Dursun, 2016; Çerçi et al., 2018, 2022; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022b; Çerçi & Koçak, ; 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia, China Japan, Korea, Extralimital: India (northwest), Pakistan.

***Lygaeus melanostolus* (Kiritshenko, 1931)**

Asian Türkiye: Niğde (Aladağlar Mts.) (Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Asia: Asian Türkiye, China, Iran, Kirgizia, Mongolia, Tadzhikistan. Extralimital: North India?

***Lygaeus simulans* Deckert, 1985**

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Ankara, Bolu Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Gümüşhane, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Malatya, Nevşehir, Niğde (Péricart, 1999a; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Özgen & Dioli, 2019; Özgen et al., 2021a; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Afghanistan, Cyprus, Iran, Central Asia. Far East.

Genus *Melanocoryphus* Stål, 1872

***Melanocoryphus albomaculatus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Center-Balkan Campus, 16.05.2017, 1 ♀; Tekirdağ Province: Şarköy-Uluman, 11.06.2017, 1 ♂. **ASIAN TÜRKİYE:** Amasya Province: Center, 14.11.2006, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Turkish Thrace (without locality information) (Péricart, 1999a, 2001), this study, first exact records for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Çankırı, Çorum, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Isparta, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Malatya, Sakarya, Van, Zonguldak (Kiritshenko, 1918, 1924; Hoberlandt, 1956; Kiyak, 1990, 1993; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 1981, 2006; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Sert et al., 2013; Küçükbasmacı & Kiyak, 2015; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2023; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Kemal & Koçak, 2018; Özgen et al., 2021a; Yazıcı, 2022b; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Iran, Iraq, Central Asia.

***Melanocoryphus tristrami* (Douglas & Scott, 1868)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Enez (Dalyan Lake), 31.08.2015, 1 ♂; Uzunköprü-Çöpköy, 16.05.2016, 1 ♀; Lalapaşa-Hacıdanışment, 07.06.2016, 1 ♂; Center, 10.10.2018, 1 ♂; İstanbul Province: Silivri-Küçüksinekli, 15.06.2016, 1 ♀; Kırklareli Province: Center-Üsküp, 21.05.2016, 2 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂. **ASIAN TÜRKİYE:** Giresun Province: Alucra-Arda village, 17.05.2006, 2 ♂♂.

European Türkiye: İstanbul, Kırklareli (Péricart, 1999a).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Bitlis, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Hatay, Isparta, İstan-

bul, İzmir, Karabük, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Niğde, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Uşak, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1916; Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Hoberlandt, 1956; Çağatay, 1995; Lodos et al., 1978, 1984, 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Dursun, 2016; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Yence & Fent, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).
Distribution in Palaearctic: Balkans, eastern Europe, European and Asian Türkiye, Egypt, Middle East, Central Asia.

Genus *Paranysius* Horváth, 1895

Paranysius fraterculus fraterculus Horváth, 1895

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Diyarbakır (Karacadağ), Erzurum, Gaziantep (Hoberlandt, 1967; Çağatay, 1995; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Yazıcı et al., 2015).

Distribution in Palaearctic: European Kazakhstan, Russia Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia, China, Mongolia, Russia.

Genus *Spilostethus* Stål, 1868

Spitostethus pandurus (Scopoli, 1763)

European Türkiye: Edirne, İstanbul, Kırklareli (Fahringer, 1922; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978; Josifov, 1986; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Çerçi et al., 2018).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bolu Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale (Bozcada, Gökçeada), Çankırı, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Hakkari, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Kilis, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Niğde, Osmaniye, Rize, Şanlıurfa, Uşak, Van, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1901, 1905, 1919; Escherich, 1897; Fahringer, 1922; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1959, 1966; Tuatay et al., 1967; Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Yiğit & Uygun, 1982; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Kıyak, 1990, 1993, 2016a; Çağatay, 1995; Péricart, 1999a; Özsaraç & Kıyak 2001; Özsaraç et al., 2001; Atlıhan et al., 2003; Tezcan & Önder, 1999, 2003; Gençer et al., 2004; Kemal & Koçak, 2008, 2018; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Öncül-Abacıgil et al., 2010; Şerban, 2010; Koçak & Kemal, 2012; Sert et al., 2013; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Çıtırkkaya et al., 2015; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Çerçi et al., 2018; Yazıcı, 2022b; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, North Africa, Middle East, Central Asia, China, Extralimital: Afrotropical Region, Australia, Oriental Region (India, Philippines).

Note: Horváth (1883) Escherich (1897) and Gadeau de Kerville (1939) mentioned this species as *Lygaeus pandurus* var. *militaris* and Horváth (1901, 1905, 1919), Fahringer (1922), Hoberlandt (1956) Lodos et al. (1999), Önder et al. (1983, 2006) mentioned as *Lygaeus pandurus*.

Spilostethus saxatilis (Scopoli, 1763)

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Tekirdağ Province: Between Saray-Bahçeköy, 18.08.2015 4 ♀♀, 7 ♂♂; between Saray-Safaalan, 18.08.2015, 8 ♀♀, 10 ♂♂. **ASIAN TÜRKİYE:** Samsun Province: Bafra, 10.07. 2005, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: İstanbul (Fahringer, 1922; Josifov, 1986).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Balıkesir, Burdur, Çanakkale (Gökçeada), Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hakkari, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul,

İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırşehir, Konya, Malatya, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sivas, Tunceli, Van, Yalova, Yozgat (Puton, 1892; Escherich, 1897; Horváth, 1901; Kiritshenko, 1918, 1924; Fahringer, 1922; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939; Hoberlandt, 1956; Linnavuori, 1965; Tutay et al., 1967; Aysev, 1974; Altınyar, 1981; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Kıyak, 1990, 1993, 2000, 2016a; Çağlar, 1992; Lodos & Önder, 1992; Çağatay, 1995; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Özsaraç et al., 2001; Kıyak et al., 2004; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Koçak & Kemal, 2012; Sert et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Kemal & Koçak, 2018; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2022; Çerçi et al., 2018; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022a, b; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, North Africa, Middle East, Central Asia, Extralimital: India?, Kashmir.

Note: Puton (1892), Escherich (1897), Horváth (1901), Kiritshenko, (1918, 1924), Fahringer (1922), Gadeau de Kerville (1939), Hoberlandt (1956), Lodos et al. (1999), Önder et al. (1983, 2006) are given this species as *Lygaeus saxatilis*.

Genus *Tropidothorsax* Bergroth, 1894

***Tropidothorax leucopterus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Enez (Taşaltı Lagoon), 31.08.2015, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Kırklareli Province:—Lüleburgaz—Kırıkköy, 15.07.2016, 1 ♀.

ASIAN TÜRKİYE: Yozgat Province: Kırkdilim, 13.03.2018, 4 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂.

European Türkiye: Edirne, Tekirdağ (Wagner, 1966; Dirik & Kıvan, 2016).

Asian Türkiye: Afyonkarahisar, Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Bartın, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Erzincan, Erzurum, Iğdır, Isparta, İzmir, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Konya, Manisa, Niğde, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883; Kiritshenko, 1918; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1966; Aysev, 1974; Çağatay, 1995; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Sert & Kabalak, 2010; Şerban, 2010; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2022; Yazıcı, 2022a, b; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, Algeria, Egypt, Central Asia, Afghanistan, Iran, Iraq, Extralimital: India.

Subfamily ORSILLINAE Ståll, 1872

Tribe NYSINI Uhler, 1876

Genus *Nysius* Dallas, 1852

***Nysius cymoides* (Spinola, 1837)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Uzunköprü road, 27.08.2015, 1 ♂; Enez (Karagöl), 01.09.2015, 2 ♂♂; Tekirdağ Province: Center-Mermer, 20.08.2015, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Uçmakdere, 20.08.2015, 1 ♀, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Edirne, Kırklareli, Tekirdağ (Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978; Josifov, 1986; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 1984, 2006).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Batman, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale (Gökçeada), Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kayseri, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Niğde (Aladağlar Mts.), Osmaniye, Siirt, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tokat, Yalova, Yozgat, Van (Horváth, 1890; Puton, 1892; Kiritshenko, 1918; Hoberlandt, 1956, 1961; Linnavuori, 1965; Lodos et al., 1978, 1984, 1999; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Önder et al., 1981, 2006; Özbek & Alaoğlu, 1987; Özbek et al., 1996; Péricart, 1999a; Tezcan & Önder, 1999; Beyaz & Tezcan, 2002; Atlıhan et al., 2003; Demirel, 2009; Öncül-Abacıgil et al., 2010; Matocq & Özgen, 2010; Özgen, 2012;

Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2023; Atakan et al., 2017; Çerçi et al., 2018; Özgen et al., 2020, 2021b; Yazıcı, 2020, 2022b; Fent et al., 2022; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023a; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, North Africa, Middle East, Central Asia, Extralimital: Cabo Verde Is., Mauritania, Sierra Leone, Sudan.

***Nysius ericae ericae* (Schilling, 1829)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Süloğlu (Dam), 15.06.2016, 22 ♀♀; Center-Balkan Campus, 08.05.2017, 1 ♀; Kırklareli Province: Pınarhisar (Mahya Hill), 30.06.2015, 1 ♀; Center-Çağlayık, 15.08.2015, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Üsküp, 22.08.2015, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: Edirne (Fent & Okyar, 2022).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Bolu Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Kilis, Manisa, Mersin, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Hoberlandt, 1956; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Kıyak, 1993, 2016; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Beyaz & Tezcan, 2002; Kıyak et al., 2004; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, North Africa, Middle East, Central Asia, China, Taiwan, Extralimital: Probably the whole of tropical Africa.

***Nysius graminicola graminicola* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Çanakkale Province: Ilgardere, 17.05.2016, 1 ♀; Edirne Province: Center--Suakacağı, 05.06.2015, 1 ♀; Uzunköprü, 27.08.2015, 5 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂; Keşan-Koru Mountains (Küçükyerlisu), 18.05.2016, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Kocahıdır, 22.07.2016, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; Mecidiye, 22.07.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Karahisar, 24.07.2016, 1 ♀; Uzunköprü-Kavacık, 14.07.2016, 7 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂; Kırklareli Province: Demirköy-Sislioba, 24.06.2015, 2 ♂♂; İğneada, 24.06.2015, 1 ♂; Center-Çağlayık, 15.08.2015, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Üsküp, 22.08.2015, 11 ♀♀, 10 ♂♂; Pınarhisar, 16.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Vize-Doğanca, 16.07.2016, 7 ♀♀, 8 ♂♂; Tekirdağ Province: Between Saray-Safaalan, 18.08.2015, 1 ♀; 11.06.2016, 4 ♀♀; Center-Mermer, 20.08.2015, 45 ♀♀, 26 ♂♂; Uçmakedere, 20.08.2015, 1 ♂; Şarköy, 21.08.2015, 5 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂; Ergene-Esenler, 17.07.2016, 1 ♀; next to the Unilever, 17.07.2016, 1 ♀; Muratlı-Hanoğlu, 17.07.2016, 3 ♀♀; Saray-Çaylaköy, 18.07.2016, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; İstanbul Province: Çatalca, 18.08.2015, 6 ♀♀, 1 ♂; between İhsaniye-Çatalca, 18.08.2015, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; İhsaniye, 11.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂; Silivri-Fenerköy, 19.08.2015, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Arnavutköy road, 12.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Çanakkale, Edirne, İstanbul, Tekirdağ, (Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978; Josifov, 1986; Önder et al., 1984, 2006).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Manisa, Mersin, Mardin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Sakarya, Sinop, Osmaniye, Uşak, Zonguldak (Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Horváth, 1901, 1905; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1966; Tuatay et al., 1967; Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Yiğit & Uygun, 1982; Önder et al., 1981, 1983, 2006; Péricart, 1999a; Yıldırım et al., 1999; Özseraç et al., 2001 as *Macroparius graminicola graminicola*; Beyaz & Tezcan, 2002; Tezcan et al., 2010; Özgen, 2012; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Dursun, 2016; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Kıyak, 2016a; Atakan et al., 2017; Yazıcı, 2022a, b; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, North Africa, Middle East, Central Asia, Far East.

***Nysius helveticus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Balıkesir, Elazığ, Erzurum, İzmir, Kars, Kastamonu, Muğla, Kayseri, Niğde (Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Kıyak, 1993; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Tezcan et al., 2010; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Atakan et al., 2017; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Özgen et al., 2021a; Eser & Dursun, 2023a; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, Iran, Iraq, Central Asia, China Russia.

***Nysius immunis* (Walker, 1872)**

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Bolu Diyarbakır, İzmir, Konya, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1890; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979 as *N. stalianus*; Lodos et al., 1999 as *N. stalianus*; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006 as *N. stalianus*; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Southern Europe, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Cyprus.

***Nysius senecionis senecionis* (Schilling, 1829)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Süloğlu (Dam), 15.06.2016, 14 ♀♀, 20 ♂♂; Center-Balkan Campus, 08.05.2017, 10 ♀♀, 8 ♂♂; Kırklareli Province: Pınarhisar-İslambeyli, 21.06.2015, 2 ♀♀; Demirköy-Boztaş, 25.06.2015, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Pınarhisar (Mahya Hill), 30.06.2015, 2 ♀♀; Tekirdağ Province: Center-Naip village, 19.08.2015, 4 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂.

European Türkiye: Çanakkale, Edirne (Hoberlandt, 1956; Josifov, 1986; Péricart, 1999a; Şerban, 2010; Fent & Okyar, 2022).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Bayburt, Bolu Bursa, Çanakkale (Gökçeada), Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Hatay, İstanbul, İzmir, Karabük, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kayseri, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Sakarya, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883; Fahringer, 1922; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Péricart, 1999a; Yıldırım et al., 1999; Öz Saraç et al., 2001 as *Tropinysius senecionis*; Önder et al., 1981, 2006; Tezcan & Önder, 2003; Şerban, 2010; Fent, 2011; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Kaya, 2018; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, North Africa, Middle East, Central Asia, Extralimital: tropical Africa.

***Nysius thymi thymi* (Wolff, 1804)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Meriç-Kadıondurma, 20.05.2016, 4 ♀♀; Kırklareli Province: Center-Çağlayık, 15.08.2015, 1 ♀, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Edirne (Fent & Okyar, 2022).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Bayburt, Çanakkale (Gökçeada), Denizli, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Kilis, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Osmaniye (Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Yıldırım et al., 1999; Beyaz & Tezcan, 2002; Önder et al., 2006; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Atakan et al., 2017; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Algeria, Asian Türkiye, Iran, Israel, Transcaucasia, Central Asia, China, Russia. Extralimital: Alaska, Canada, USA.

Tribe ORSILLINI Stål, 1872

Genus *Belonochilus* Uhler, 1871***Belonochilus numenius* (Say 1832)****European Türkiye:** Edirne (Fent & Dursun, 2021).**Asian Türkiye:** İzmir (Çerçi & Oruz, 2021)**Distribution in Palaearctic:** Wide distribution in Europe. Madeira, Asian Türkiye. Extralimital: North America (Canada, Mexico, USA).**Genus *Camptocoris* Puton, 1886*****Camptocoris longicornis* (Puton, 1874)****Asian Türkiye:** Hatay (Amanus Mountains) (Seidenstücker, 1960a; Péricart, 1999a).**Distribution in Palaearctic:** Europe: Crete, Greece, Italy, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia.**Genus *Orsillus* Dallas, 1852*****Orsillus depressus* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)****Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE:** Tekirdağ Province: Şarköy-Yeniköy, 11.06.2017, 1 ♀, 1 ♂.**European Türkiye:** This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.**Asian Türkiye:** Adana, Amasya, Antalya, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Elazığ, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Konya, Mersin, Niğde (Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023a; Yence & Fent, 2023).**Distribution in Palaearctic:** Wide distribution in Europe and North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Cyprus, Iran, Central Asia, China.***Orsillus maculatus* (Fieber, 1861)****Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE:** Edirne Province: Enez-Gülçavuş (coastal path), 23.07.2016, 5 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂.**European Türkiye:** This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.**Asian Türkiye:** Adana, Amasya, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bursa, Çanakkale, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kilis, Mersin, Niğde (Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2016; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).**Distribution in Palaearctic:** Southern and Eastern Europe, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Middle East.***Orsillus reyi* Puton, 1871****European Türkiye:** İstanbul (Horváth, 1918; Josifov, 1986; Önder *et al.*, 2006).**Asian Türkiye:** Adana, Antalya, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Mersin (Seidenstücker, 1958; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Péricart, 1999a).**Distribution in Palaearctic:** Southern Europe, Algeria, Tunisia, Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Israel.**Genus *Ortholomus* Stål, 1872*****Ortholomus carinatus* (Lindberg, 1932)****Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE:** Tekirdağ Province: Between Saray-Safaalan, 11.06.2016, 1 ♀.**European Türkiye:** Edirne (Hoberlandt, 1956; Josifov, 1986; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006).**Asian Türkiye:** Balıkesir, Bilecik, Çanakkale, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Isparta, Karaman, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Konya, Mardin, Niğde (Aladağlar Mts.), (Lodos et al., 1978, 1999 as *Nysius carinatus*; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979 as *N. carinata*; Önder et al., 2006, as *N. carinatus* and *O. carinatus*; Péricart, 1999a; Özşaraç et al., 2001; Matocq et al., 2014;

Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Europe: European Kazakhstan, European Türkiye, France, Greece, Portugal, Spain, Ukraine. North Africa: Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia. Asia: Asian Türkiye, Iran, Iraq.

***Ortholomus punctipennis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Center-Suakacağı, 05.07.2015, 2 ♀♀; Uzunköprü-Mestanlar, 14.07.2016, 1 ♀; Kırklareli Province: Center-Çağlayık, 15.08.2015, 5 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Üsküp, 22.08.2015, 5 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Çukurpınar, 22.08.2015, 3 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Tekirdağ Province: Between Saray-Safaalan, 11.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 6 ♂♂.

European Türkiye: Edirne, İstanbul (Belgrad Forest), (Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978; Josifov, 1986; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006).

Asian Türkiye: Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Bolu Burdur, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, Karabük, Kars, Kayseri, Nevşehir, Sivas, Uşak. (Kiritshenko, 1918; Hoberlandt, 1956; Linnavuori, 1965; Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Çağlar, 1992; Péricart, 1999a; Kıyak, 2000; Önder et al., 2006; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Eser & Dursun, 2023a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Central Asia, China, Cyprus, Iran, Korea, Mongolia, Russia.

Note: Lodos et al., 1978, 1999, Kıyak, 2000, Önder et al., 2006, Kıyak & Akar, 2010; mentioned this species as as *Nysius punctipennis*.

Subfamily ISCHNORHYNCHINAE Stål, 1872

Genus *Kleidocerys* Stephens, 1829

***Kleidocerys ericae* (Horváth, 1908)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: İstanbul Province: Çatalca-Dağyenice, 12.06.2016, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bolu Bursa, Düzce, İstanbul, Karaman, Kocaeli, Konya, Muğla, Sinop, Sivas, Zonguldak (Lodos et al., 1978, 1999 as *Kleidocerys truncatus ericae* and *K. truncatus truncatus*; Önder et al., 1981, 2006 as *K. truncatus ericae* and *K. truncatus truncatus*; Şerban, 2010)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Crete, France, Ireland, Netherlands, Spain. North Africa: Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia. Asia: Asian Türkiye.

***Kleidocerys resedae resedae* (Panzer, 1797)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Kırklareli Province: Demirköy-Sivriler, 27.06.2015, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: Turkish Thrace (Péricart, 2001a), this study, the first exact record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Balıkesir, Erzurum, İstanbul (Çamlıca), Muğla (Aysev, 1974; Yıldırım et al., 1999; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015).

Distribution in Palaearctic: (including *ericae*) Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Central Asia, Far East.

Note: *Kleidocerys resedae* is a Holarctic element and is known in Eurasia, from the Iberian Peninsula to Japan, reaching the latitude of 65°N in Scandinavia, and present in Siberia to the Far East. It does not seem to be known from North Africa. It is also present in Canada and the USA. In middle and southern Europe, its distribution area overlaps that of *Kleidocerys ericae*, and in the absence of reliable discriminative characteristics, it is impossible to draw a reliable distribution map

(Péricart, 1999a). Owing to the confusion with *Kleidocerys resedae*, which has almost the same chorology, only the distribution area of the complex *resedae-ericae* is given (Aukema 2018).

Family OXYCARENIDAE Ståll, 1862

Subfamily OXYCARENINAE Ståll, 1862

Genus *Auchenodes* Horváth, 1891

***Auchenodes capito* Horváth, 1891**

Asian Türkiye: Gaziantep (Lodos *et al.*, 1999).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Asia: Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Jordan.

***Auchenodes costalis* (Lethierry, 1877)**

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Balıkesir, Bursa, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Kayseri, Osmaniye, Van (Seidenstücker, 1958, Péricart, 1999b; Yazıcı *et al.*, 2015).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Bulgaria, Greece, Portugal, Spain. Asia: Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Georgia, Syria.

Genus *Brachyplax* Fieber, 1860

***Brachyplax tenuis* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Havsa-Hasköy (Saksağan Stream), 21.05.2016, 11 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂. İstanbul Province: Çatalca-İhsaniye, 11.06.2016, 1 ♀; Akalan Bridge, 14.06.2016, 1 ♀; Dağyenice, 12.06.2016, 1 ♂; Silivri-Küçüksinekli, 15.06.2016, 1 ♂. Kırklareli Province: Center-Üsküp, 21.05.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Edirne (Hoberlandt, 1956; Josifov, 1986; Péricart, 1999b; Önder *et al.*, 2006).

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Ankara, Elazığ, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Mersin, Niğde (Horváth, 1901; Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Seidenstücker, 1958; Aysev, 1974; Çağatay, 1986; Lodos *et al.*, 1999; Péricart, 1999b; Önder *et al.*, 2006; Matocq *et al.*, 2014; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023b; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe and in North Africa. Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Transcaucasia, Central Asia, Syria.

Note: Horváth (1901), Linnavuori, (1953), Hoberlandt (1956), Seidenstücker, (1958), Çağatay, (1986), Lodos *et al.* (1999) and Önder *et al.* (2006) mentioned this species as *Brachyplax palliata*.

Genus *Camptotelus* Fieber, 1860

***Camptotelus lineolatus lineolatus* (Schilling, 1829)**

Asian Türkiye: Ankara, Bolu (Abant Lake), Kayseri, Konya, Sivas (Horváth, 1905; Péricart, 1999b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Kirgizia, Mongolia, Russia, Uzbekistan.

***Camptotelus parallelus* Horváth, 1894**

Asian Türkiye: Aksaray, Ankara, Kayseri, Niğde (Seidenstücker, 1957; Péricart, 1999b)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Iran, Central Asia.

Genus *Leptodemus* Reuter, 1900

***Leptodemus minutus* (Jakovlev, 1874)**

European Türkiye: Çanakkale, Edirne, Tekirdağ (Lodos *et al.*, 1978).

Asian Türkiye: Afyonkarahisar, Aydın, Bilecik, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale (Gökçeada), Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, İzmir, Manisa, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kilis, Kütahya, Manisa, Muğla, Siirt, Şanlıurfa, Uşak (Seidenstücker, 1960a; Çağatay, 1986, 1995; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Péricart, 1999b; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Önder et al., 2006; Matocq & Özgen, 2010; Sert et al., 2013; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Yazıcı & Sertkaya 2020; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: European Kazakhstan, Italy, Russia (ST), Spain, Ukraine. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia, Extralimital: Sudan.

Note: Yazıcı & Sertkaya (2020) found that this species caused damage by colonizing young seedlings of cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum*) in high numbers in Hatay, and caused wilting and deformation of the leaves with the intense suction they made.

Genus *Macroplax* Fieber, 1860

Macroplax fasciata fasciata (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Canakkale Province: Ilgardere, 17.05.2016, 5 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Between Behramlı-Şehitlik, 17.05.2016, 8 ♀♀, 12 ♂♂; between Eceabat-Kilitbahir, 17.05.2016, 5 ♀♀, 11 ♂♂; Edirne Province: Uzunköprü-Ömerbey, 16.05.2016, 40 ♀♀, 22 ♂♂; Keşan-Koru Mountains (Küçükyerlisu), 18.05.2016, 2 ♀♀; Kocahıdır, 22.07.2016, 1 ♂; Meriç-Kadıdondurma, 20.05.2016, 10 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Kırklareli Province: Demirköy-Boztaş, 25.06.2015, 1 ♀; Istranca, 25.06.2015, 1 ♀; Hamdibey, 26.06.2015, 49 ♀♀, 55 ♂♂; between Hamdibey-Yeşilce, 26.06.2015, 28 ♀♀, 22 ♂♂; Vize-Kıyıköy, 28.06.2015, 4 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂; Center-Üsküp, 21.05.2016, 1 ♂; 06.06.2016, 3 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Çukurpınar, 21.05.2016, 1 ♀; Tekirdağ Province: Between Saray-Safaalan, 18.08.2015, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; 11.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; Ergene-Esenler, 17.07.2016, 1 ♂; İstanbul Province: Çatalca-Danamandıra 11.06.2016, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; between Çatalca-İhsaniye, 11.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂; Akalan Bridge, 14.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 9 ♂♂; Arnavutköy road, 12.06.2016, 4 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; Dağyenice, 12.06.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Silivri-Küçüksinekli, 15.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂ **ASIAN TÜRKİYE:** Amasya Province: Havza-İlca village, 12.07.2002, 1 ♂; Hatay Province: Hassa-Akbez, 19.05.2010, 1 ♀; Aktepe, 20.05.2010, 1 ♀; Tokat Province: Niksar-Kümbetli, 20.06.2006, 3 ♀♀; Reşadiye-Kündüryan, 28.08.2005, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: Çanakkale, Edirne, İstanbul, Tekirdağ, (Fahringer, 1922; Çağatay, 1986; Lodos et al., 1978).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Bursa, Çanakkale (Gökçeada), Çorum, Denizli, Düzce, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırşehir, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Sinop, Uşak, Zonguldak (Aladağlar Mts.), Uşak (Horváth, 1883, 1905; Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Aysev, 1974; Özbek et al., 1996; Çağatay, 1986, 1995; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Péricart, 1999b; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Matocq & Özgen, 2010; Öncül-Abacıgil et al., 2010; Fent, 2011; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Çıtırıkaya et al., 2015; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Kıyak, 2016a; Çerçi et al., 2018; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022b; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023b; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Middle East.

Macroplax preysleri (Fieber, 1837)

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Uzunköprü-Çöpköy, 08.06.2016, 1 ♀. **ASIAN TÜRKİYE:** Artvin Province: Şavşat-Şalçı, 21.07.2005, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: This study. New record for the Turkish Thrace.

Asian Türkiye: Akşehir, Kastamonu (Péricart, 1999b; Fent & Dursun, 2016a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye.

Genus *Macropternella* J.A. Slater, 1957

***Macropternella inermis* (Fieber, 1851)**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Antalya, Mersin (Seidenstücker, 1957, 1958; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999b; Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Bosnia Hercegovina, Crete, Greece, Serbia, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East, Central Asia, Extralimital: Ethiopia, Sudan.

Genus *Metopoplax* Fieber, 1860

***Metopoplax fuscinervis* Stål, 1872**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Lalapaşa-Hacıdanışment, 07.06.2016, 1 ♂; İpsala road (20. km) 08.06.2016, 6 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; Uzunköprü-Mestanlar, 14.07.2016, 1 ♀; İstanbul Province: Silivri-Küçüksinekli, 15.06.2016, 5 ♀♀; Kırklareli Province: Pınarhisar-İslambeyli, 21.06.2015, 23 ♀♀, 12 ♂♂; between Yenice-Demirköy (around sand pit), 21.06.2015, 13 ♀♀, 10 ♂♂; Demirköy-İğneada (Longoz Forest), 27.06.2015, 6 ♀♀, 11 ♂♂; Istranca, 25.06.2015, 2 ♀♀; Boztaş, 26.06.2015, 38 ♀♀, 28 ♂♂; Vize-Kıyıköy, 28.06.2015, 10 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂; Pınarhisar (Mahya Hill), 30.06.2015, 99 ♀♀, 87 ♂♂; Üsküp, 22.08.2015, 1 ♂; Tekirdağ Province: Malkara, between Yaylaköy-Yaylagöne, 22.06.2017, 1 ♀. **ASIAN TÜRKİYE:** Samsun Province: Bafra, 10.07.2005, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Edirne (Hoberlandt, 1956; Péricart, 1999b; Önder et al., 2006).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Bursa, Çanakkale (Gökçeada), Denizli, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Karabük, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Mersin, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883; Hoberlandt, 1956; Kaya & Hıncal, 1991; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999b; Kıyak, 2000; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Önder et al., 2006; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Southern and Central Europa, European and Asian Türkiye, Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia, Cyprus, Iran, Israel.

***Metopoplax origani* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Kırklareli Province: Center-Beypinar, 22.05.2016, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Deveçatağı, 04.06.2016, 2 ♂♂; Babaeski, 09.06.2016, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; Pınarhisar, 16.06.2016, 3 ♀♀; Demirköy-Boztaş, 26.06.2015, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Vize-Kıyıköy, 28.06.2015, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Edirne Province: Uzunköprü road, 27.08.2015 1 ♀; 08.06.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Süloğlu (Dam), 15.06.2016, 22 ♀♀, 19 ♂♂; Uzunköprü-Çöpköy, 16.05.2016, 3 ♀♀; Meriç-Olacak village, 19.05.2016, 1 ♀; 08.06.2016, 1 ♀; Meriç-Akıncılar road, 19.05.2016, 1 ♀; Havsa-Hasköy (Saksağan Stream), 21.05.2016, 1 ♂; Enez-Hisarlı, 31.08.2015, 1 ♂; Center-Balkan Campus, 08.05.2017, 14 ♀♀, 13 ♂♂; 16.05.2017, 31 ♀♀, 27 ♂♂; İstanbul Province: Arnavutköy road, 12.06.2016, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Silivri-Küçüksinekli, 15.06.2016, 12 ♀♀, 13 ♂♂; Tekirdağ Province: Between Saray-Safaalan, 11.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; **ASIAN TÜRKİYE:** Sivas Province: Akıncılar-Sevindik village 21.09.2007, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Çanakkale, Edirne, Kırklareli (Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978; Josifov, 1986; Önder et al., 1984; Péricart, 1999b; Fent & Okyar, 2022).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Aksaray, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bolu Burdur, Bursa, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırşehir, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Uşak, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1905, 1918; Reuter, 1890; Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Tuatay et al.,

1967; Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Çağatay, 1986; Péricart, 1999b; Tezcan & Önder, 1999; Kıyak, 2000; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; İner & Tezcan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Dursun, 2016; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Atakan et al., 2017; Çerçi et al., 2018; Özgen et al., 2021b; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Middle East, Central Asia.

Genus *Microplax* Fieber, 1860

Microplax albofasciata (A. Costa, 1847)

Material examined: **EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE:** Edirne Province: Uzunköprü road, 08.06.2016, 2 ♂♂; Kırklareli Province: Vize–Kıyıköy, 28.06.2015, 1 ♂.

European Türkiye: Edirne, İstanbul, Tekirdağ (Hoberlandt, 1956; Sienkiewicz, 1964; Lodos et al., 1978; Josifov, 1986; Péricart, 1999b; Önder et al., 2006).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Bursa, Bolkar Mountains (Konya, Mersin, Niğde) Bursa, Erzincan, Gaziantep, Karaman, Kayseri, Kütahya, Mersin, Uşak (Horváth, 1883; Reuter, 1890; Linnavuori, 1953; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Özbek et al., 1996; Péricart, 1999b; Önder et al., 2006; Öncül–Abacıgil et al., 2010; Sert et al., 2013; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, Algeria, Tunisia, Israel.

Microplax interrupta (Fieber, 1837)

Material examined: **EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE:** Çanakkale Province: between Eceabat–Kilitbahir, 17.05.2016, 1 ♂; Edirne Province: Meriç–Olacak village, 19.05.2016, 2 ♀♀; Lalapaşa–Hacıdanışment, 07.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 8 ♂♂; Süloğlu (Dam), 15.06.2016, 1 ♂; İstanbul Province: Silivri–Küçüksinekli, 15.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Kırklareli Province: Pehlivan köyü, 19.06.2015, 1 ♀; Demirköy–between Hamdibey–Yeşilce, 26.06.2015, 1 ♂; Vize–Kıyıköy, 28.06.2015, 10 ♀♀, 7 ♂♂; Tekirdağ Province: Between Saray–Safaalan, 11.06.2016, 2 ♂♂.

European Türkiye: Edirne (Hoberlandt, 1956; Josifov, 1986; Péricart, 1999b; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Okyar, 2022).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Diyarbakır, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır (Ararat Mountain), Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Konya, Mardin, Mersin (Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Çağatay, 1986; Lodos et al., 1984, 1999; Péricart, 1999b; Önder et al., 2006; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Kıyak, 2016a; Yazıcı, 2022b; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023b; Yence & Fent, 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. European and Asian Türkiye, North Africa, Transcaucasia, Middle East, Central Asia, China, Mongolia, Russia.

Microplax limbata Fieber, 1864

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Diyarbakır, Gaziantep, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Mersin, Nevşehir, Niğde (Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Çağatay, 1986; Kıyak, 1993; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999b; Önder et al., 2006; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Greece. Asia: Asian Türkiye, Middle East.

Note: The type locality of this species is “Klein Asien” (Péricart, 2001a).

Genus *Oxycarenus* Fieber, 1851

Subgenus *Euoxycarenus* Samy, 1969***Oxycarenus pallens* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)**

Material examined: **EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE:** Çanakkale Province: Between Behramlı–Şehitlik, 17.05.2016, 1 ♂; Edirne Province: Uzunköprü–Ömerbey, 16.05.2016, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Çöpköy, 16.05.2016, 3 ♀♀; 08.06.2016, 1 ♂; Çavuşlu, 14.07.2016, 3 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂; Meriç–Akıncılar road, 19.05.2016, 1 ♀; Olacak village, 19.05.2016, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Havsa–Hasköy (Saksağan Stream), 21.05.2016, 1 ♀; Lalapaşa–Hacıdanışment, 07.06.2016, 1 ♂; İpsala road (20. km) 08.06.2016, 2 ♂♂; Süloğlu (Dam), 15.06.2016, 15 ♀♀, 9 ♂♂; İstanbul Province: Between Çatalca–İhsaniye, 11.06.2016, 1 ♂; Dağyenice, 12.06.2016, 1 ♂; Silivri–Küçüksinekli, 15.06.2016, 4 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Kırklareli Province: Pehlivan köyü, 19.06.2015, 1 ♀; Lüleburgaz–Evrensekiz, 14.05.2016, 1 ♀; Center–Kavakdere, 03.06.2016, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; Deveçatağı, 04.06.2016, 2 ♀♀; Beypınar, 06.06.2016; 1 ♀; Üsküp, 06.06.2016, 4 ♀♀; Üsküpdere, 16.06.2016, 2 ♂♂; Pınarhisar, 16.06.2016, 1 ♂; Pınarhisar–İslambeyli, 21.06.2015, 5 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; between Yenice–Demirköy (around sand pit), 21.06.2015, 8 ♀♀, 6 ♂♂; Demirköy–İğneada (Longoz Forest), 27.06.2015, 1 ♀; Tekirdağ Province: Center–Mermer, 20.08.2015, 3 ♀♀; between Saray–Safaalan, 11.06.2016, 1 ♀; Malkara–Izgar village, 22.06.2017, 15 ♀♀, 14 ♂♂; Ahmetpaşaköy, 22.06.2017, 1 ♂; between Yaylaköy–Yaylagöne, 22.06.2017, 10 ♀♀, 8 ♂♂.

European Türkiye: Çanakkale, Edirne (Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978; Josifov, 1986; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Okyar, 2022).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bolu Burdur, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırşehir, Kilis, Konya, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Siirt, Sinop, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Van, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Tuatay et al., 1967; Aysev, 1974; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Önder et al., 1983, as *O. pallens*, 2006, Çağatay, 1986, 1995 *O. longiceps*; Lodos et al., 1984, 1999 as *O. longiceps*; Péricart, 1999b; as *O. longiceps* and *O. pallens*; Özbek et al., 1996; Kıyak, 2000; Kıyak et al., 2004; Öncül–Abacıgil et al., 2010; Matocq & Özgen, 2010; Kemal & Balkan, 2011; Koçak & Kemal, 2012; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2023; Dursun, 2016; Fent & Dursun, 2016a; Kemal & Koçak, 2018; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022b; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Middle East, Central Asia, China, Mongolia, Russia, Extralimital: India, Sudan.

Subgenus *Oxycarenus* Fieber, 1837***Oxycarenus hyalinipennis* (A. Costa, 1843)**

Material examined: **EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE:** Edirne Province: Kocahıdır, 22.07.2016, 1 ♀.

European Türkiye: Çanakkale (Şerban, 2010).

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Çankırı, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, İstanbul (Erenköy), İzmir, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kilis, Konya, Mersin, Muğla, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sinop (Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Linnavuori, 1953; Hoberlandt, 1956; Aysev, 1974; Çağatay, 1986; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 1983, 2006; Péricart, 1999b; Bektaş & Tezcan, 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015, 2023; Atakan et al., 2017; Yazıcı, 2022b; Eser & Dursun, 2023b).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Balkans, Southern Europe, North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Middle East. Extralimital: Oriental Region, tropical and South Africa, and introduced in South America.

***Oxycarenus lavaterae* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Material examined: EUROPEAN TÜRKİYE: Edirne Province: Center, 10.07.2021, 5 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂ (on *Tilia* sp.)

European Türkiye: İstanbul (Sarıyer) (Arslangündoğdu et al., 2018)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Saudi Arabia, Yemen. Extralimital: tropical and South Africa.

***Oxycarenus modestus* (Fallén, 1829)**

Asian Türkiye: Bolkar Mountains (Konya, Mersin, Niğde), Kahramanmaraş, Yalova (Linnavuori, 1953; Lodos et al., 1978, 1999; Péricart, 1999b; Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, China.

Genus *Tropidophlebia* Kerzhner, 1964***Tropidophlebia costalis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)**

Asian Türkiye: Niğde (Aladağlar Mts.) (Yence & Fent, 2023)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Asian Türkiye, Asian Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Russia.

Family PACHYGRONTHIDAE Stål, 1865**Subfamily PACHYGRONTHINAE Stål, 1865****Tribe TERACRIINI Stål, 1872****Genus *Cymophyes* Fieber, 1870*****Cymophyes ochroleuca* Fieber, 1870**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Antalya, Çanakkale, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Gaziantep, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Konya, Menderes River Basin, Mersin, Nevşehir (Linnavuori, 1953; Seidenstücker, 1953a; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1999; Péricart, 1999a; Önder et al., 2006; Şerban, 2010; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Albania, Crete, Greece. North Africa: Egypt, Libya. Asia: Asian Türkiye, Middle East.

Family PIESMATIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843**Subfamily PIESMATINAE Amyot & Serville, 1843****Genus *Parapiesma* Péricart, 1974*****Parapiesma atriplicis* (Frey-Gessner, 1863)**

Asian Türkiye: Erzurum, Niğde, Kars (Yıldırım et al., 2013)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Bulgaria, European Kazakhstan, Greece, Moldavia, Romania, Russia, Ukraine. Asia: Asian Türkiye, Central Asia, China.

***Parapiesma kolenatii* (Fieber, 1861)**

Asian Türkiye: Adıyaman (Nemrut Mountain), Ağrı, Aksaray, Bitlis, Kars, Kayseri, Van (Kiritshenko, 1918; Linnavuori, 1965; Awad & Önder, 1997 as *Piesma kolenatii*; Önder et al., 2006; Heiss & Péricart, 2007; Kemal & Koçak, 2018)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Asia: Azerbaijan, Türkiye.

***Parapiesma quadratum* (Fieber, 1844)**

European Türkiye: Kırklareli (Fent & Dursun, 2019).

Asian Türkiye: Çanakkale (Gökçeada) (Heiss & Péricart, 1983, 2007; Awad & Önder, 1997).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Middle East, China, Kirgizia, Korea, Mongolia, Russia.

***Parapiesma salsolae* (Becker, 1867)**

Asian Türkiye: Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Çankırı, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, İzmir, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırşehir, Nevşehir, Niğde, Samsun (Hoberlandt, 1956; Heiss & Péricart, 1983, 2007; Awad & Önder, 1997 as *Piesma salsolae*; Kiyak et al., 2004 as *Piesma salsolae*; Yıldırım et al., 2013)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Central and Southern Europe, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, China, Iran, Mongolia, Russia.

Genus: *Piesma* Lepeletier & Serville, 1828***Piesma capitatum* (Wolff, 1804)**

Asian Türkiye: Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Aydın, Kars, Kocaeli (Kiritshenko, 1918; Hoberlandt, 1956; Awad & Önder, 1997; Önder et al., 2006; Heiss & Péricart, 2007)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. Egypt, Asian Türkiye, Central Asia, Far East.

***Piesma maculatum* (Laporte, 1833)**

Asian Türkiye: Amasya, Balıkesir, Bartın, Çankırı, Erzurum, Kastamonu, Samsun (Ege & Onat 1982; Awad & Önder, 1997; Yıldırım & Özbek 1990; Öncül-Abacıgil et al., 2010; Önder et al., 2006; Heiss & Péricart, 2007; Yıldırım et al., 2013; Eser & Dursun, 2023b; Yazıcı et al., 2023).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Wide distribution in Europe. North Africa, Asian Türkiye, Transcaucasia, Central Asia, Far East.

Records in need of confirmation**Family ARTHENEIDAE Stål, 1872*****Artheneis aegyptiaca* Lindberg, 1939**

Asian Türkiye: ?Kastamonu (Péricart, 1999a).

Distribution in Palaearctic: North Africa: Egypt, Libya, Morocco?, Asia: Arab Emirates, Asian Türkiye?, Iran, Iraq?, Israel, Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Sinai, Yemen. Extralimital: Sudan.

Note: Péricart (1999a) described this species from Kastamonu in Anatolia with “?”. The existence of the species, which has no other records so far, needs to be confirmed in Türkiye.

***Artheneis wagneri* Ribes, 1972**

Asian Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Çanakkale, Elazığ, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Niğde (Péricart, 1999a; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Bulgaria, Crete, Greece, Macedonia, Spain. Asia: Armenia, Asian Türkiye?, Azerbaijan, Iran, Syria.

Note: Péricart (1999a) mentioned that considering the work of Kerzhner (1997) showing the variability and proximity of two species (*A. wagneri* and *A. intricata*), the Anatolian series of this species that he had previously examined possibly represented some or all *A. intricata*.

Family GEOCORIDAE Baerensprung, 1860***Geocoris arenarius* (Jakovlev, 1867)**

Asian Türkiye: Antalya, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Konya, Mersin (Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Çakır & Önder, 1990; Kaya & Hıncal, 1991; Büyük & Özpınar, 1999; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Kaplan 2007).

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Albania, Crete, European Kazakhstan,

Greece, Hungary, Italy, Moldavia, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Ukraine. Asia: Asian Kazakhstan, Armenia?, Azerbaijan?, China, Mongolia, Russia, Tadzhikistan, Uzbekistan.

Note: According to Kerzhner (1979) records from Israel, Syria, Egypt, Iran, and probably Türkiye are erroneous and probably concern *G. fedtschenkoi* (Aukema 2018).

Family LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829

***Horvathiolus fulvescens* (Puton, 1874)**

Asian Türkiye: Gaziantep? (Seidenstücker, 1960a, as *Melanocoryphus fulvescens*; Péricart, 1999a)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Spain. North Africa: Algeria, Libya, Tunisia. Asia: Asian Türkiye?

Note: Pericart (1999a) reports that this species is a Western Mediterranean element known from Southern Spain, Algeria, Tunisia and Libya, and its presence in Anatolia needs to be confirmed.

***Ortholomus Jordani* Hoberlandt, 1953**

Asian Türkiye: Antalya, Gaziantep, Hatay (Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006)

Asia: Iraq.

Note: Aukema (2018) reports that the validity of this species, known only from Iraq, needs to be confirmed due to its similarity to *O. carinatus* and scarcity of the material (two specimens from the same locality). In this case, the validity of the species must be verified for the records in Türkiye to be accurate.

Family OXYCARENIDAE Stål, 1862

***Metopoplax ditomoides* (A. Costa, 1847)**

Asian Türkiye: Çankırı, İzmir (Yazıcı, 2022b; Yazıcı et al., 2022)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, France, Great Britain, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, Malta, Macedonia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Serbia, Spain, Switzerland. North Africa: Algeria, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia. Extralimital (introduced): North America (USA).

Note: The record of this species given by Yazıcı (2022b) from İzmir is based on M.S.K. Ghauri's diagnosis in 1972. The second record, 50 years later, was made by Yazıcı et al. (2022) from Çankırı Province. The distribution of the species in the Palaearctic Region points to the west of Türkiye. This species needs to be confirmed in Türkiye.

Family PIESMATIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Parapiesma silenes* (Horváth, 1888)**

Asian Türkiye: Erzurum (Awad & Önder, 1997 as *Piesma silenes*)

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Austria, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Czech Republic, Kazakhstan, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Russia (ST) Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Ukraine. Asia: Asian Kazakhstan.

Note: The record from Türkiye (Hoberlandt, 1956a: 85) refers to *salsolae* (Aukema 2018). Apart from this, the record given by Awad & Önder (1997) from Erzurum needs to be confirmed considering the Palaearctic distribution of the species.

Table 2. Check-list of Lygaeoidea (excluding Rhyparochromidae) of Türkiye. ET = European Türkiye, AT = Asian Türkiye, records in need of further confirmation are marked with '?', accepted records but without any exact published locality known to us are marked by a circle '●', the species recorded for the first time in Turkish Thrace are marked by an asterisk "*"

ARTHENEIDAE Stål, 1872		
<i>Artheneis aegyptiaca</i> Lindberg, 1939		AT?
<i>Arthenis alutacea</i> Fieber, 1861		AT
<i>Artheneis balcanica</i> (Kormilev, 1938)		AT
<i>Artheneis foveolata</i> Spinola, 1837		AT
<i>Artheneis hyrcanica</i> (Kolenati, 1845)		AT
<i>Artheneis intricata</i> O.S. G. Putshkov, 1969		AT
<i>Artheneis wagneri</i> Ribes, 1972		AT?
<i>Holcocranum saturejæ</i> (Kolenati, 1845)	ET	AT
BERYTIDAE Fieber, 1851		
<i>Apoplymus pectoralis</i> Fieber, 1859	ET	AT
<i>Neides aduncus</i> Fieber, 1859		AT
<i>Neides afghanus</i> Seidenstücker, 1968		AT
<i>Neides brevipennis</i> Puton, 1895		AT
<i>Neides tipularius</i> (Linné, 1758)	ET	AT
<i>Berytinus clavipes</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	ET	AT
<i>Berytinus hirticornis nigrolineatus</i> (Jakovlev, 1903)	ET	AT
<i>Berytinus hirticornis pilipes</i> (Puton, 1875)		AT
<i>Berytinus minor minor</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	ET	AT
<i>Berytinus consimilis</i> (Horváth, 1885)		AT
<i>Berytinus distinguendus</i> (Ferrari, 1874)	ET?	AT
<i>Berytinus geniculatus</i> (Horváth, 1885)		AT
<i>Berytinus montivagus</i> (Meyer-Dür, 1841)	ET	AT
<i>Berytinus setipennis</i> (Saunders, 1876)		AT
<i>Berytinus signoreti</i> (Fieber, 1859)		AT
<i>Berytinus striola</i> (Ferrari, 1874)		AT
<i>Gampsocoris culicinus culicinus</i> Seidenstücker, 1948	ET	AT
<i>Gampsocoris culicinus melitenus</i> Seidenstücker, 1965	ET?	AT
<i>Gampsocoris enslini</i> Seidenstücker, 1953	ET	AT
<i>Gampsocoris punctipes pallidus</i> Hoberlandt, 1951		AT

<i>Gampsocoris punctipes punctipes</i> (Germar, 1822)	ET	
<i>Metacanthus annulosus</i> (Fieber, 1859)		AT
<i>Metacanthus meridionalis</i> (A. Costa, 1843)	ET	AT
<i>Metatropis rufescens</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)		AT
BLISSIDAE Stål, 1862		
<i>Blissus hirtulus</i> Burmeister, 1835		AT
<i>Blissus putoni</i> Jakovlev, 1875		AT
<i>Dimorphopterus blissoides</i> (Baerensprung, 1859)	ET*	AT
<i>Dimorphopterus doriae</i> (Ferrari, 1874)	ET*	AT
<i>Dimorphopterus spinolae</i> (Signoret, 1857)	ET*	AT
<i>Ischnodemus caspius</i> Jakovlev, 1871	ET*	AT
<i>Ischnodemus genei</i> (Spinola, 1837)		AT
<i>Ischnodemus sabuleti</i> (Fallén, 1826)	ET	AT
<i>Ischnodemus suturalis</i> Horváth, 1883	ET	AT
CYMIDAE Baerensprung, 1860		
<i>Cymodema tabida tabida</i> Spinola, 1837	ET*	AT
<i>Cymus aurescens</i> Distant, 1883	ET	AT
<i>Cymus clavicularis</i> (Fallén, 1807)	ET	AT
<i>Cymus glandicolor</i> Hahn, 1832	ET	AT
<i>Cymus gracilicornis</i> Vidal, 1940		AT
<i>Cymus melanocephalus</i> Fieber, 1861	ET	AT
<i>Cymus turcicus</i> Matocq, 2000		AT
GEOCORIDAE Baerensprung, 1860		
<i>Bledionotus systellonotoides</i> Reuter, 1878		AT
<i>Geocoris chloroticus</i> Puton, 1888		AT
<i>Geocoris arenarius</i> (Jakovlev, 1867)		AT?
<i>Geocoris ater</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	ET	AT
<i>Geocoris grylloides</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)		AT
<i>Geocoris lapponicus</i> Zetterstedt, 1838		AT
<i>Geocoris lineola lineola</i> (Rambur, 1839)	ET*	AT
<i>Geocoris megacephalus</i> (Rossi, 1790)	ET	AT
<i>Geocoris pallidipennis pallidipennis</i> (A. Costa, 1843)	ET*	AT
<i>Geocoris phaeopterus</i> (Germar, 1838)		AT
<i>Geocoris pubescens</i> (Jakovlev, 1871)		AT
<i>Geocoris erythrocephalus</i> (Lepelletier & Serville, 1825)	ET	AT
<i>Geocoris luridus</i> (Fieber, 1844)		AT

<i>Geocoris nebulosus</i> (Montandon, 1907)		AT
<i>Geocoris putonianus</i> Bergroth, 1892		AT
<i>Engistus exsanguis exsanguis</i> Stål, 1872		AT
<i>Engistus salinus</i> (Jakovlev, 1874)		AT
<i>Henestaris halophilus</i> (Burmeister, 1835)	ET*	AT
<i>Henestaris kareli</i> Hoberlandt, 1956		AT
<i>Henestaris laticeps laticeps</i> (Curtis, 1836)	ET	AT
HETEROGASTRIDAE Stål, 1872		
<i>Heterogaster affinis</i> Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835		AT
<i>Heterogaster artemisiae</i> Schilling, 1829	ET	AT
<i>Heterogaster cathariae</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)		AT
<i>Heterogaster urticae</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	ET	AT
<i>Platyplax inermis</i> (Rambur, 1839)	ET*	AT
<i>Platyplax salviae</i> (Schilling, 1829)		AT
LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829		
<i>Apterola kuenckeli kuenckeli</i> Mulsant & Rey, 1866		AT
<i>Apterola kuenckeli rubicunda</i> (Stål, 1872)		AT
<i>Apterola lownii</i> (Saunders, 1876)	ET	AT
<i>Arocatus longiceps</i> Stål, 1872	ET	AT
<i>Arocatus melanocephalus</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	ET	AT
<i>Arocatus roeselii</i> (Schilling, 1829)	ET*	AT
<i>Caenocoris nerü</i> (Germar, 1847)		AT
<i>Graptostethus servus servus</i> (Fabricius, 1787)		AT
<i>Horvathiolus kiritshenkoi kiritshenkoi</i> (Horváth, 1916)		AT
<i>Horvathiolus fulvescens</i> (Puton, 1874)		AT?
<i>Horvathiolus superbus</i> (Pollich, 1781)	ET	AT
<i>Horvathiolus syriacus</i> (Reuter, 1885)	ET	AT
<i>Lygaeosoma anatolicum</i> Seidenstücker, 1960	ET*	AT
<i>Lygaeosoma angulare</i> Reuter, 1885		AT
<i>Lygaeosoma sardeum sardeum</i> Spinola, 1837	ET*	AT
<i>Lygaeosoma sardeum erythropterum</i> (Puton, 1876)		AT
<i>Lygaeosoma sibiricum</i> Seidenstücker, 1962		AT
<i>Lygaeus creticus</i> Lucas, 1854		AT
<i>Lygaeus equestris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	ET	AT
<i>Lygaeus melanostolus</i> (Kiritshenko, 1931)		AT

<i>Lygaeus simulans</i> Deckert, 1985		AT
<i>Melanocoryphus albomaculatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	ET•	AT
<i>Melanocoryphus tristrami</i> (Douglas & Scott, 1868)	ET	AT
<i>Paranysius fraterculus fraterculus</i> Horváth, 1895		AT
<i>Spitostethus pandurus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	ET	AT
<i>Spitostethus saxatilis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	ET	AT
<i>Tropidothorax leucopterus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	ET	AT
<i>Nysius cymoides</i> (Spinola, 1837)	ET	AT
<i>Nysius ericae ericae</i> (Schilling, 1829)	ET	AT
<i>Nysius graminicola graminicola</i> (Kolenati, 1845)	ET	AT
<i>Nysius helveticus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)		AT
<i>Nysius immunis</i> (Walker, 1872)		AT
<i>Nysius senecionis senecionis</i> (Schilling, 1829)	ET	AT
<i>Nysius thymi thymi</i> (Wolff, 1804)	ET	AT
<i>Belonochilus numenius</i> (Say 1832)	ET	AT
<i>Camptocoris longicornis</i> (Puton, 1874)		AT
<i>Orsillus depressus</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)	ET*	AT
<i>Orsillus maculatus</i> (Fieber, 1861)	ET*	AT
<i>Orsillus reyi</i> Puton, 1871	ET	AT
<i>Ortholomus carinatus</i> (Lindberg, 1932)	ET	AT
<i>Ortholomus jordani</i> Hoberlandt, 1953		AT?
<i>Ortholomus punctipennis</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)	ET	AT
<i>Kleidocerys ericae</i> (Horváth, 1908)	ET*	AT
<i>Kleidocerys resedae resedae</i> (Panzer, 1797)	ET•	AT
Family OXYCARENIDAE Stål, 1862		
<i>Auchenodes capito</i> Horváth, 1891		AT
<i>Auchenodes costalis</i> (Lethierry, 1877)		AT
<i>Brachyplax tenuis</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)	ET	AT
<i>Camptotelus lineolatus lineolatus</i> (Schilling, 1829)		AT
<i>Camptotelus parallelus</i> Horváth, 1894		AT
<i>Leptodemus minutus</i> (Jakovlev, 1874)	ET	AT
<i>Macroplox fasciata fasciata</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	ET	AT
<i>Macroplox preysleri</i> (Fieber, 1837)	ET*	AT
<i>Macropternella inermis</i> (Fieber, 1851)		AT
<i>Metopoplax ditomoides</i> (A. Costa, 1847)		AT?

<i>Metopoplax fuscineris</i> Stål, 1872	ET	AT
<i>Metopoplax origani</i> (Kolenati, 1845)	ET	AT
<i>Microplax albofasciata</i> (A. Costa, 1847)	ET	AT
<i>Microplax interrupta</i> (Fieber, 1837)	ET	AT
<i>Microplax limbata</i> Fieber, 1864		AT
<i>Oxycarenus pallens</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)	ET	AT
<i>Oxycarenus hyalinipennis</i> (A. Costa, 1843)	ET	AT
<i>Oxycarenus lavaterae</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	ET	
<i>Oxycarenus modestus</i> (Fallén, 1829)		AT
<i>Tropidophlebia costalis</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)		AT
PACHYGRONTHIDAE Stål, 1865		
<i>Cymophyes ochroleuca</i> Fieber, 1870		AT
PIESMATIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843		
<i>Parapiesma atriplicis</i> (Frey-Gessner, 1863)		AT
<i>Parapiesma kolenatii</i> (Fieber, 1861)		AT
<i>Parapiesma quadratum</i> (Fieber, 1844)	ET	AT
<i>Parapiesma salsolae</i> (Becker, 1867)		AT
<i>Parapiesma silenes</i> (Horváth, 1888)		AT?
<i>Piesma capitatum</i> (Wolff, 1804)		AT
<i>Piesma maculatum</i> (Laporte, 1833)		AT
TOTAL - ET:71 species 2 species ? AT:137 species 7 species ?		

DISCUSSION

In this study, an updated list of the Turkish Lygaeoidea superfamily (except Ryhparochromidae) is presented along with the species identified as a result of field studies conducted in the Thrace Region between 2015–2020. As a result of the study conducted in 91 localities in the Thrace Region, 53 species belonging to 7 families (Artheneidae–1, Blissidae–5, Cymidae–5, Geocoridae–6, Heterogastridae–2, Lygaeidae–24, Oxycarenidae–10) were identified. 16 of them –*Dimorphopterus blissoides* (Baerensprung, 1859), *D. doriae* (Ferrari, 1874) *D. spinolae* (Signoret, 1857) *Ischnodemus caspius* Jakovlev, 1871, *Cymodema tabida tabida* Spinola, 1837, *Geocoris lineola lineola* (Rambur, 1839) *G. pallidipennis pallidi-*

pennis (A. Costa, 1843) *Henestaris halophilus* (Burmeister, 1835), *Platyplax inermis* (Rambur, 1839), *Arocatus roeselii* (Schilling, 1829) *Lygaeosoma anatolicum* Seidenstücker, 1960 *L.sardeum sardeum* Spinola, 1837, *Orsillus depressus* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852) *O. maculatus* (Fieber, 1861), *Kleidocerys ericae* (Horváth, 1908) *Macroplax preysleri* (Fieber, 1837) – were recorded for the first time from Turkish Thrace. *Cymodema tabida tabida*, *Arocatus roeselii* and *Macroplax preysleri* are rarely distributed species that were previously detected in only two localities in Anatolia. The first exact locality records are given in this study for the *Melanocoryphus albo-maculatus* (Goeze, 1778) and *Kleidocerys resedae resedae* (Panzer, 1797), which

were previously given without any locality information from the Thrace Region.

Additionally, as a result of reviewing the studies carried out in Türkiye so far (between 1883 and 2023) it has been determined that 49 genera and 146 species/subspecies belonging to 10 families (Artheneidae, Berytidae, Blissidae, Cymidae, Geocoridae, Heterogastridae, Lygaeidae, Oxycarenidae, Pachygronthidae, Piesmatidae) from the Lygaeoidea superfamily (except Ryhparochromidae) are distributed. However, 7 of them [*Artheneis aegyptiaca* Lindberg, 1939, *A. wagneri* Ribes, 1972, *Geocoris arenarius* (Jakovlev, 1867), *Horvathiolus fulvescens* (Puton, 1874), *Ortholomus jordani* Hoberlandt, 1953, *Metopoplax ditomoides* (A. Costa, 1847), *Parapiesma silenes* (Horváth, 1888)] has been identified as a species that is likely to be confused with related species or has a low probability of being found in Türkiye considering their Palaearctic distribution, and more evidence is needed to include these species in the Turkish list. Except for the species that need to be verified, the distribution of other species according to families is as follows: Artheneidae 6 species (1 in European, 6 in Asian Türkiye), Berytidae 24 species (10 in European, 23 in Asian Türkiye), Blissidae 9 species (6 in European, 9 in Asian Türkiye), Cymidae 7 species (5 in European, 7 in Asian Türkiye) Geocoridae 19 species (7 in European, 19 in Asian Türkiye), Heterogastridae 6 species (3 in European, 6 in Asian Türkiye), Lygaeidae 42 species (27 in European, 42 in Asian Türkiye), Oxycarenidae 19 species (11 in European, 18 in Asian Türkiye),

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Pachygronthidae 1 species (only in Asian Türkiye) and Piesmatidae 6 species (1 in European, 6 in Asian Türkiye).

Type localities of *Neides brevipennis* Puton, 1895, *Gampsocoris culicinus melitenus* Seidenstücker, 1965, *Ischnodemus suturalis* Horváth, 1883, *Gampsocoris enslini* Seidenstücker, 1953, *Cymus turcicus* Matocq, 2000, *Henestaris kareli* Hoberlandt, 1956, *Lygaeosoma anatolicum* Seidenstücker, 1960 and *Microplax limbata* Fieber, 1864 are Anatolia and *Cymus turcicus* and *Henestaris kareli* are endemic to Anatolia. *Horvathiolus kiritshenkoi kiritshenkoi* (Horváth, 1916), *Parapiesma kolenatii* (Fieber, 1861) are species with a limited distribution in Anatolia and its immediate surroundings, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan and Iran.

When compared to the number of species in the Palaearctic Region, based on the 10 families in this study, there are 105 genera and 561 species/subspecies in the Palaearctic Region, and Türkiye constitutes approximately 25% of the number of species in the Palaearctic Region with 139 species/subspecies. This study also draws attention to Türkiye's species richness.

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